

AN IMPROVED MODEL FOR RF SIGNAL ANALYSIS WITH NEURAL NETWORKS USING HYPERPARAMETER TUNING

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BY

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I, Shivanta Sahoo declare that the work presented in this dissertation entitled “An Improved Model for RF Signal Analysis with Neural Networks using Hyperparameter Tuning” submitted to the Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering, in the Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Shri Venkateshwara University, Uttar Pradesh, India, for the award of the Master of Technology in Electronics & Communication Engineering an original work. I have neither plagiarized nor submitted the same work for the award of any other degree. In case this undertaking is found incorrect, my degree may be withdrawn unconditionally by the University.

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ABSTRACT

This dissertation discusses models for signal analysis using neural networks. At this time neural networks have shown significant results in various fields including bio-medical ECGs, automation driving and large language models. It also has potential for implementation in signal analysis in the RF range. Radio frequency is the most widely used electromagnetic wave spectrum for communication, for that it has motivated us to pursue this research.

By going through various review articles and scholarly papers, this dissertation highlights the various models of neural networks and the methods implemented in signal analysis. Many of the neural networks modals have been written over the years, each network having some advantages over the other. This study provides a brief description neural network modals and provides a comparative analysis. Based on this analysis, this study puts forward hybrid convolutional neural network- long short term memory network also know as CNN-LSTM neural network, that aids in proper signal analysis.

The neural network can be implemented in a number of programming languages, keeping the model's algorithm indistinguishable. While conducting this research, python language was adopted and tensor-flow library by Google was used.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TITLE PAGE	ii
DECLARATION	iii
CERTIFICATE OF ORIGINAL WORK	iv
CERTIFICATE OF THE RECOMMENDATION	v
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	vi
ABSTRACT	vii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	xii
LIST OF TABLES	viii
LIST OF FIGURES	xiii
LIST OF SYMBOLS	xv
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	xvii
1. CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1-34
1.1 IMPORTANCE OF RADIO FREQUENCY	8
1.2 BENEFITS OF NEURAL NETWORKS IN VARIOUS FIELDS AND RELATED WORKS	12
1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT	14
1.4 ADDRESSING THE SIGNAL ANALYSIS	15
1.5 AIM AND OBJECTIVE	17
1.6 PROPOSED MODELS	18
1.7 SCOPE OF RESEARCH WORK	19
2. CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	20-48
2.1 FUNDAMENTALS OF SIGNALS	21

1.1.1 SIGNAL REPRESENTATIONS	22
1.1.2 RF SIGNAL MODULATIONS	23
1.1.3 ENERGY SIGNALS AND POWER SIGNALS	25
1.1.4 CORRELATION	26
1.1.5 SIGNAL ENTROPY	27
2.2 FUNDAMENTALS OF SIGNAL ANALYSIS	28
1.2.1 FOURIER TRANSFORM	28
1.2.2 SHORT FOURIER TRANSFORM	28
1.2.3 POWER SPECTRAL DENSITY	29
1.2.4 WAVELET TRANSFORM	29
1.2.5 HILBERT TRANSFORM	30
1.2.6 HILBERT- HUANG TRANSFORM	31
1.2.7 WIGNER – VILE DISTRIBUTION	32
2.3 FUNDAMENTALS OF NEURAL NETWORKS	33
1.3.1 BASIC IDEA BEHIND NEURAL NETWORKS	33
1.3.2 PERCEPTRON	36
1.3.3 BAYES CLASSIFIER	37
1.3.4 KNN	39
1.3.5 LINEAR REGRESSION	40
1.3.6 LOGARITHMIC REGRESSION	40
1.3.7 SIMPLE RNN	40
1.3.8 CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS	41
1.3.9 LTSM	43
1.3.10 GRU	46
1.3.11 HYBRID MODELS	47
3. CHAPTER 3: NEURAL NETWORK TERMINOLOGIES	49-52

3.1 METRICS OF PERFORMANCE	50
3.2 TRAINING	50
3.3 ACCURACY	50
3.4 LOSS FUNCTION	50
3.5 ACTIVATION FUNCTION	51
3.5 CONFUSION MATRIX	51
3.6 EPOCHS	51
3.7 FAULT TOLERANCE	52
3.8 COMPLEXITY REGULARISATIONS	52
3.9 NETWORK PRUNING	52
4. CHAPTER 4: DATA PREPROCESSING	53-56
4.1 FORMATS OF DATASET	54
4.2 MISSING VALUES	55
4.3 DATA SAMPLING	55
4.4 DATA SEGMENTATION	55
4.5 PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS	56
5. CHAPTER 5: FEATURE EXTRACTION METHODS	57-63
5.1 TIME DOMAIN METHODS	58
5.2 TRANSFORM BASED METHODS	59
5.3 SIGNAL DECOMPOSITION METHODS	61
5.4 ENVELOP BASED METHODS	62
6. CHAPTER 6: NEURAL NETWORK LIFECYCLE	64-66
7. CHAPTER 7: METHODOLOGY AND APPROACH	67-73
7.1 DATASET AND PREPROCESSING	68
7.2 MODEL IMPLEMENTATION	70

7.2.1 MODEL CNN	70
7.2.2 MODEL CNN-LSTM	72
8. CHAPTER 8: MODEL EVALUATION	74-75
9. CHAPTER 9: RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	76-83
10. CONCLUSION AND SCOPE FOR FURTHER WORK	84-87
REFERENCES	xxii
APPENDIX-A	xxxix
APPENDIX-B	xxxix
APPENDIX-C	xxxix
APPENDIX-D	xlviii

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title	Page No.
Table 2.1	Neural Networks	47
Table 4.1	File types in Data Science	53

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Title	Page No.
Figure 1.1	Neural Network	3
Figure 1.2	Neural Network detailed	6
Figure 1.3	Single Neuron	6
Figure 1.4	Range of Frequencies	8
Figure 1.5	Architecture of CNN-LSTM	17
Figure 2.1	Waveform of Peacock's Voice	20
Figure 2.2	Time-domain and Frequency-Domain	21
Figure 2.3	Sigmoid Function	34
Figure 2.4	ReLU Function	34
Figure 2.5	Tanh Function	35
Figure 2.6	Perceptron	36
Figure 2.7	Naive Bayes Classification	37
Figure 2.8	K-nearest Neighbors	38
Figure 2.9	Typical Architecture of CNN	40
Figure 2.10	Typical Architecture of LSTM	44
Figure 6.1	AI Lifecycle	64
Figure 7.1	Architecture of CNN	68
Figure 7.2	Architecture of CNN-LSTM	70
Figure 9.1	Accuracy vs Epochs of CNN	75
Figure 9.2	Loss vs Epochs of CNN	75
Figure 9.3	Confusion Matrix of CNN	76
Figure 9.4	Accuracy vs Epochs of CNN-LSTM	78

Figure 9.5	Loss vs Epochs of CNN	79
Figure 9.6	Confusion Matrix of CNN	79

LIST OF SYMBOLS

Symbol	Details
E	Energy
P	Power
$H(X)$	Entropy
$\hat{f}(\omega)$	Fourier Transform
$X(\tau, \omega)$	Short Fourier Transform with window functional
$S(\omega)$	Power Spectral Density
Ψ	Wavelet function
$\hat{x}(t)$	Hilbert Transform
$AF(\tau)$	Ambiguity Function
σ	Activation Function
$\hat{y}$	Predicted Class
${}_n C_k$	Combination of n objects, chosen k at a time-averaged

Σ

Sigma; Summation

 Π

Pi (Product) Notation

PHOTOGRAPHS

Photograph No.	Title	Page No.
Photograph 1.1	Cellphone Tower	11
Photograph 2.1	John McCarthy: Computer scientist known as the father of AI	33
Photograph 10.1	Global INDIAai Summit 2024	87

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Details
AF	Ambiguity function
AM	Amplitude Modulation
ASK	Amplitude Shift Keying
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CNN-LSTM	Convolutional Neural Network - Long Short-Term Memory
CRO	Cathode Ray Oscilloscope
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CWT	Continuous Wavelet Transform
DL	Deep Learning
DWT	Discrete Wavelet Transform
EHF	Extremely High Frequency
ELF	Extremely Low Frequency
EMD	Empirical Mode Decomposition)
FM	Frequency Modulation
FGPA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
FSK	Frequency Shift Keying
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format version 5
HF	High Frequency

HHT	Hilbert-Huang Transform
HSA	Hilbert Spectral Analysis
IMFs	Intrinsic Mode Functions
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbors
LMS	Least Mean Squares
LF	Low Frequency
ML	Machine Learning)
MF	Medium Frequency)
MSK	Minimum Shift Keying
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PM	Phase Modulation
PSD	Power Spectral Density
PSK	Phase Shift Keying
QAM	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
QPSK	Quadrature Phase Shift Keying
RAM	Random Access Memory
RF	Radio Frequency
RLS	Iterative Least Squares
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SHF	Super High Frequency
SLF	Super Low Frequency
SQL	Structured Query Language
STFT	Short-Time Fourier Transform
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition

TXT	Text file format
UHF	Ultra High Frequency
ULF	Ultra Low Frequency
VHF	Very High Frequency
VLF	Very Low Frequency
WVD	Wigner-Ville Distribution
XML	Extensible Markup Language

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

In the early years of development, artificial intelligence remained limited to logic functions and functional programming. Later, the development of back propagation algorithm and two other modals namely recurrent neural network(RNN) and convolutional neural network(CNN), all proved to show significant improved results in processing data. Further developments in layering of neural networks improved the resolution of data processing. The audio signal processing could then be performed with the help of layered RNN and CNN structures.

Signals in radio frequency domain are electromagnetic wave traversing through the space with a directional component. Often the underlying motivation is to transmit information from one place to another. There are two important parts of a communication system namely Transmitter section, to transmit signals and Receiver section, to capture the radio signals. Signals are processed in both of these sections to overcome noise, increase the transmitting distance and encode the signals. Signal processing involves manipulating, transforming, or modifying signals to extract useful information or achieve specific objectives. Signal analysis, on the other hand, primarily focuses on understanding and characterizing signals to extract meaningful insights or information.

In Classical domain, the signal analysis has focused on identifying oscillatory components present in the signal by implementing a number of techniques. These techniques include Fourier analysis and signal spectra, sampling and quantization, signal filtering and convolution, autocorrelation and statistical signal processing.

Non-classical signal analysis includes wavelet transforms, compressed and sparse signal analysis, adaptive filtering of least mean squares (LMS) or iterative least squares (RLS), compressed sensing and gradient descent, machine learning for signal analysis, and depth layers. Some of these, called input units, are designed to take in various types of information from the outside world that the network will attempt to understand, recognize, or otherwise process. Other units are located on the other side of the network and send signals that tell the network how to respond to the information it has learned; one or more layers of hidden units lie between the input device and the output device, and together these make up the majority of the neural network. Most neural networks are fully connected, meaning that every hidden unit and every output unit is connected to every unit in the layer on either side. The connection between one unit and another is represented by a number called a weight; This number can be positive (if one unit leads to another) or negative (if one unit leads to another). The heavier it is, the greater the effect one unit has on another unit. (This refers to the way the brain's electrical connections are made through tiny gaps called synapses.)

Figure 1.1 Neural network

Information flows through neural networks in two primary ways: during the learning phase (training) and during normal operation (post-training). Data samples are introduced into the network through input devices, which initiate a sequence of hidden processes, culminating in the production of an output. This architecture is known as a feed-forward network. Not all components are active simultaneously; each unit receives input from the preceding unit, and the strength of this input is moderated by the weight of the connection it traverses. In its simplest form, each unit aggregates the inputs it receives. To illustrate this concept, consider learning to play bowling. When you first pick up a heavy ball and roll it down the lane, your brain monitors the speed and trajectory of the ball, noting how close it comes to knocking down the pins. The next time you bowl, you recall what went wrong, adjust your actions, and aim for a better result. This process involves comparing the desired outcome with the actual outcome, identifying discrepancies, and making adjustments based on these differences, such as "I need to throw harder," "I need to adjust

my aim to the left," or "I need to maintain my stance." In neural networks, a similar process occurs, known as backpropagation. This involves comparing the network's output with the expected output (the ground truth) and using the discrepancy to adjust the weights of the connections between units, working backward from the output layer to the hidden layers. Over time, backpropagation enables the network to learn by minimizing the difference between the actual output and the expected output, eventually reducing this difference to near zero (minimizing the mean squared error), thereby refining the network's response.

Once the network is sufficiently trained with a variety of learning models, it reaches a stage where it can be presented with new, unseen data and its responses can be observed. For instance, suppose the network has been trained with a series of images of chairs and tables (encoded in a format it can process) and has been instructed to classify each image as either a chair or a table. After being exposed to 25 different chairs and 25 different tables, the network can then be tested with images of new designs it has not encountered before to see how it classifies them. Depending on the training it received, the network will attempt to categorize these new patterns as either chairs or tables based on its prior learning. It is important to note that the neural network does not perceive the furniture in the same way humans do; it does not "see" the items. Instead, the input to the network is in the form of binary numbers, where each pixel in an image is represented as either on or off. For example, an image of a chair might be represented as 10110, while an image of a table might be represented as 01001.

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) are related but distinct concepts, often used interchangeably. Machine learning typically requires human intervention during the

training phase, whereas deep learning algorithms can operate without human intervention. Neural networks, which are a subset of machine learning, play an important role in deep learning, enabling it to function.

Machine learning encompasses a range of algorithms and learning models, such as linear regression, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), decision trees, and clustering methods like K-Means. These techniques allow machine learning algorithms to adapt to new situations and discover patterns in data. Machine learning relies heavily on data, with supervised learning involving training a model using labelled data, such as classifying emails as spam or not spam. In supervised learning, the computer is provided with the correct answers during training. In contrast, unsupervised learning does not require labelled data. Methods like K-Means clustering can be used to identify patterns or groupings in the data without prior knowledge of the categories. This allows the algorithm to learn the structure of the data independently.

Deep learning, a branch of machine learning, requires larger datasets for training than traditional machine learning methods. It excels at tasks like facial recognition, text analysis, and natural language processing (NLP), which involve extracting meaningful information from images or text. Deep learning's capability to learn from data is powered by neural networks, which can mimic human-like understanding and decision-making processes.

Neural networks facilitate deep learning techniques, particularly in areas where traditional machine learning approaches may struggle, such as vision and language processing. They can emulate the way neurons in the human brain communicate, allowing deep learning systems to develop insights and solve complex problems efficiently.

Figure 1.2 Neural network detailed

Through above complex structure data can be absorbed providing a set segmented inputs to the first layer of neurons. This layer h1 of the neurons are connected with the second layer of the neurons h2. Forming the next layer of computations.

The set of interconnected neurons can be represented as:

$$Y(n) = x_1 + x_2 w_2 + \dots + x_n w_n + B \quad (1.1)$$

where B is bias in eqn. (1)

If we consider individual neurons or perceptrons in a neural network, we get

Figure 1.3 Single Neuron

Figure 1.1 shows a diagram representing a single neuron or perceptron in a neural network. It has the following components:

- a) Inputs: These are the input features to the neuron. In this case, there are two inputs,
- b)Weights :Each input is multiplied by a corresponding weight. The weights determine the influence of each input on the output.
- c)Summation: The weighted inputs are summed up to produce a weighted sum, denoted as
- d)Activation Function ($f(z)$): This function is applied to the weighted sum to produce the output, The activation function introduces non-linearity into the model, enabling it to learn complex patterns.

In prior to feeding the data into these interconnected neurons, it usually or in most cases as we say needs to be preprocessed. There are various types and formats of data in which can be stored. A detailed description of these formats of data is discussed in the topic 4.1, chapter 4.

Through the application of preprocessing techniques such as dimensionality reduction and batch segmentation, we turn the data into readable form for the 1st layer of neuron structure. the benefit of preprocessing is not limited to just changing the data into readable but also has a role in improving the final results of the neural network. This can be seen in various papers where prepossessing the data has improved the accuracy. The Neural lifecycle is discussed in detailed manner in chapter 6. It throws theoretical insight into the internal mechanisms undergoing during the simulations. The methodology used in this

study, are discussed in chapter 7. This chapters delve into how neural networks can be trained and fine-tuned for signal analysis. The results and discussion sections will delve into the findings of the study, highlighting the main points of the improved modal in analysing radio frequency signals.

1.1 IMPORTANCE OF RADIO FREQUENCY

Nearly 104 years ago, on November 2, 1920, the Westinghouse Electric Manufacturing Company in Pittsburgh first broadcast under the name KDKA. This was a significant achievement because it led to the beginning of the use of radio waves as a medium of news and information. It allows data to be transmitted for long periods of time without the need for a physical connection.

Figure 1.4 Range of Frequencies

The details of each frequency band and their applications:

ELF (Extremely Low Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 3 Hz to 30 Hz
- Applications: Submarine communication, geophysical exploration, and monitoring of the Earth's ionosphere and magnetosphere.

SLF (Super Low Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 30 Hz to 300 Hz
- Applications: Communication with submarines, long-range communication through the Earth's crust.

ULF (Ultra Low Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 300 Hz to 3 kHz
- Applications: Communication with submarines, studies of the Earth's ionosphere, seismology.

VLF (Very Low Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 3 kHz to 30 kHz
- Applications: Navigation, time signals, submarine communication, and geophysical monitoring.

LF (Low Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 30 kHz to 300 kHz
- Applications: AM broadcasting, navigation systems, and marine communication.

MF (Medium Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 300 kHz to 3 MHz
- Applications: AM radio broadcasting, maritime communication, and navigation.

HF (High Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 3 MHz to 30 MHz
- Applications: Shortwave radio broadcasting, amateur radio, aviation communication, and over-the-horizon radar.

VHF (Very High Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 30 MHz to 300 MHz
- Applications: FM radio broadcasting, television broadcasting, land mobile communication, air traffic control, and two-way radio systems.

UHF (Ultra High Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 300 MHz to 3 GHz
- Applications: Television broadcasting, mobile phones, Wi-Fi, GPS, Bluetooth, and radar.

SHF (Super High Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 3 GHz to 30 GHz
- Applications: Microwave communication, satellite communication, radar, wireless LAN, and mobile phone networks.

EHF (Extremely High Frequency)

- Frequency Range: 30 GHz to 300 GHz

- Applications: High-frequency microwave communication, radio astronomy, and experimental research in telecommunications.

Photograph 1.1: Cellphone Tower

So to summarize, in modern day radio waves have wide applications in AM and FM radio, television broadcasting, cell phones, and Wi-Fi networks. RADAR, on the other hand, utilizes radio waves to detect the presence of objects in a particular area for intrusions. The RADAR also has its application in predicting upcoming storms and cyclones. It is being used by carrier ships for navigation purpose in oceans.

1.2 BENEFITS OF NEURAL NETWORKS IN VARIOUS FIELDS AND RELATED WORKS

In a paper by Zuogang Shang, a neural network termed the Signal Processing Informed Neural Network was introduced. This framework integrates signal processing knowledge into the deep learning model. It was applied to develop a Denoising fault-aware wavelet network, which combines wavelet convolution with dynamic hard thresholding, index-based soft filtering, and a classifier. This network showed significant improvement in diagnostic performance compared to other explainable or denoising deep learning networks[10].

Denoising is one application of neural networks. Jens Oppliger et al.[11] proposed a weak signal extraction method that involves denoising diffraction data. Their system acts as a neural-aware noise filter.

Brian Shevitski et al. designed a modified deep neural network for solving RF domain problems. This network combines an auto-encoder convolutional network with a transformer network to leverage feature extraction and attention mechanisms[12].

Daniel Morton provided a signal analysis tool capable of identifying the source of a target using machine learning. Their model could locate the source by extracting key features, including the angle of arrival[13].

Matthew Setzler et al.[14] demonstrated how deep learning can generate signals closely resembling original modulations and provided methods for spectral filling using deep neural networks.

Jiamiao Yan showed that CNNs could be applied in computer vision tasks, including image quality enhancement, object classification, and segmentation, broadening the range of neural network applications [15].

Abul Kalam Azad et al.[16] experimentally demonstrated the use of artificial neural networks (ANN) to process sensing signals from a Brillouin optical time-domain analyzer (BOTDA).

Several healthcare applications have shown that neural networks can identify diseases from data, capturing patterns in terminally ill patients. Zhang contributed a multi-modal fusion method for Alzheimer's disease based on discrete cosine transform convolutional sparse representation [17].

Fabian J. Theis's study [18] highlighted how neural networks aid in signal analysis in immunology, offering a range of proven and new methods for bio-signal analysis .

Wan-Ju Lin presented a deep learning neural network for predicting surface roughness in milling products, proposing three hybrid models: Fast Fourier Transform-Deep Neural Networks, Fast Fourier Transform-Long Short Term Memory Network, and one-dimensional convolutional neural network [19].

In a review by Sang Ho Choi [20], the use of spiking neural networks in analyzing biomedical signals, such as electroencephalograms, electrocardiograms, and electromyograms, was discussed.

Heikki Huttunen explored deep learning from a signal processing perspective, emphasizing its significance in modern self-driving cars [21].

Alexandr Slavutskiy demonstrated a neural network for real-time signal processing, focusing on non-linear distortion filtering [22].

G.F. Fortino et al. introduced a CNN algorithm for analyzing data from active target time projection chambers, simplifying the analysis of large datasets produced in these experiments [23].

Xianlu Pan recently revisited the applications of artificial neural networks in signal processing, discussing the origins, types, and research progress of ANN in this field [24].

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Translating data into a meaningful form in signal analysis is the main problem; this data is usually distorted by noise, contains unrelated elements, and has distortions. The traditional signal processing methods may encounter challenges as they tackle contemporary large sets of complex data. This is where neural networks, more importantly, deep learning models come to play.

Neural networks can learn and extract features from data without being told how to do it. In applications like signal analysis, where signals are often non-linear and highly varying, this is particularly useful. However, there are a number of difficulties that arise when implementing neural networks in signal analysis. Usually big amounts of labelled samples are needed for training neural networks. For instance medical diagnostics or

RF signal processing have their own requirements for obtaining and labelling such kind of information which requires much time and money. Furthermore signals may suffer from noise or artifacts that may reduce quality of data resulting in lower performance of models. “Black boxes” are the common names given to deep learning models like CNNs or RNNs due to their opacity. It becomes hard to understand why they make decisions when there’s no transparency involved.

Training and deploying neural networks, especially deep architectures, require substantial computational resources. This can be a barrier for small organizations or those operating in resource-constrained environments. Neural networks can easily overfit to the training data, particularly when the data set is small or not representative of real-world scenarios. This results in models that perform well on training data but poorly on new, unseen data.

Different types of signals pose unique challenges. For instance, audio signal analysis might require handling temporal dependencies and varying signal lengths, while biomedical signal analysis might need to account for physiological differences across individuals.

1.4 ADDRESSING THE SIGNAL ANALYSIS GOAL

Implementing Neural network to process micro and macro data within the spectrum.

Micro and macro data often come from diverse points within the spectrum and have different characteristics. For instance, micro data might involve granular data points,

while macro data might be more abstract and generalized. Integrating these into a neural network framework poses challenges. It requires careful preprocessing and normalization from dataset point of view to ensure that the model can learn effectively from data. This diversity poses challenges in feature extraction and representation, as CNNs may excel in processing structured data but struggle with abstract macro-level information.

Micro data often comes with a high resolution and detailed information, while macro data is more aggregated. This scale difference also leads to challenges in model training, as the neural network must learn to integrate and balance information from different resolutions. A common approach is to use CNN layers to downsample micro data, bringing it closer in scale to macro data. However, this can result in the loss of long term signal characteristics information.

CNNs are particularly adept at handling spatial data and identifying local patterns. However, they may not capture temporal dependencies or sequential information effectively. To address this, a proposed CNN-LSTM model combines the strengths of CNNs in feature extraction with the ability of LSTMs to manage both short term and long term characteristics of the signal. The CNN component can process spatial or short-term patterns, while the LSTM layer can capture long-term dependencies.

Issues and challenges

Neural networks, particularly deep architectures, are prone to overfitting, especially when trained on micro data with limited variability. Overfitting occurs when the model learns to memorize training data rather than generalize from it. This issue is compounded when incorporating macro data, which may introduce noise or less

relevant features. Regularization techniques, such as dropout, weight regularization, and data augmentation, can help mitigate overfitting. Additionally, careful cross-validation and testing on diverse datasets are essential to ensure that the model generalizes well to new data.

One of the major challenges in deploying CNN-LSTM models is their interpretability. While these models can achieve high performance, they are often viewed as "black boxes," making it difficult to understand how they arrive at specific decisions. This lack of transparency can be an issue in domains where trust and accountability are important.

1.5 AIMS AND OBJECTIVE

This dissertation serves the following purposes:

Aim 1: To run existing CNN model

To build, code and run the model in compatible device.

Aim 2: To run hybrid CNN-LSTM

To build, code and run the model in compatible device.

Aim 3: To compare their performance

To provide a descriptive analysis of both the model's performance.

The research includes implementation of libraries or numpy array to implement model architectures. Python is chosen to be the language of choice as it is a versatile and adaptable when it comes to neural networks.

1.6 PROPOSED HYBRID CNN-LSTM MODEL

Model Description

Figure 1.5 Architecture of CNN-LSTM

CNN1 and CNN2: There are two separate Convolutional Neural Network layers. CNNs are typically used to extract spatial features from data from in-phase and quadrature component of signal. Each CNN operates on different inputs or possibly the same input with different parameters or configurations.

Concatenate: After feature extraction by CNN 1 and CNN 2, the outputs from these layers are concatenated. This operation merges the feature maps or feature vectors from the two CNNs, allowing the combined representation to be used in subsequent layers.

Long Short Term Memory: The concatenated features are fed into an LSTM layer. LSTMs are the type of Recurrent Neural Network well-suited for processing sequential data and capturing long-term dependencies. This layer processes the sequence of features obtained from the CNNs, capturing temporal relationships or patterns.

Output with One-Hot Encoding: The output from the LSTM layer is likely passed through a dense fully connected layer to produce the final output, which is one-hot encoded. One-hot encoding is used for classification tasks, where the output represents categorical classes.

1.7 SCOPE OF RESEARCH WORK

This research work contains results from a particular dataset of RF signal which has been previously also used in researches. The dataset was of simulated RF signals which contained Additive White Gaussian Noise, therefore it is not the representation of real world signals. The designed models were run on 16 GB RAM and AMD Ryzen 7 CPU, not on GPUs which are comparatively faster, so results may vary in higher end setup.

CHAPTER 2

Literature Review

In this chapter a brief review of topics under artificial neural networks is covered. The Reader will be able to learn about existing research and articles. This chapter serves to provide an overview of current knowledge of neural networks, their types and common terminologies used within deep learning.

2.1 FUNDAMENTALS OF SIGNALS

A signal is a function that conveys information about the behaviour or attributes of some phenomenon, and it can be a function of time, space, or any other independent variable.

Figure 2.1 Waveform of Peacock's voice

Signals can be classified into different varieties such as analog signals that are continuous and vary smoothly over time, and digital signals that are discrete and have a limited number of values at distinct points in time. Signals can also be deterministic, where they can be described exactly by a mathematical equation, or random, where they display some level of uncertainty and are characterized statistically. Signal representation may exist either in the time domain, when signal is given as a function of time; or frequency domain which describes the signal in terms of its frequency components usually obtained by Fourier Transform. Moreover, there is also what we call time-frequency representation which gives both time and frequency information together for non-stationary signals. Signals possess several important characteristics like amplitude that refers to the strength of the signal; frequency that stands for the periodicity rate of the signal; phase indicating an exact position on waveform based on some point in previous timeline. The alternation between periodic which repeating over an amount of time and aperiodic which are non-repeating, is typical for signals.

2.1.1 SIGNAL REPRESENTATIONS

Signal Representations are done in three categories

1. Time domain representations.
2. Frequency domain representations.
3. Time-Frequency representations

Signal representation can be in various forms, primarily time-domain, frequency-domain, and time-frequency domain.

Figure 2.2 Time-domain and Frequency-domain

Time-domain representation means a signal is represented as a function of time, describing how the amplitude of signal varies over time. This representation is intuitive and very good for understanding real-time behaviors of signals. Time-domain analysis,

where one typically looks at the waveform directly and may calculate statistical measures such as mean or variance to identify patterns in or anomalies on a signal.

A signal in the frequency domain is described by its spectral content which portions of the signal fall into each given band. It boils down to the Fourier Transform, which turns your time-domain signal into frequency elements. Frequency Domain Representation: It conveys the spectral characteristics of a signal, i.e. what is/are dominant frequency and their amplitudes etc. that we need to understand about an input signal before implementing it into system application circuit.

Time-frequency domain: Representation that combines time and frequency information at the same time. This is quite convenient, specifically when dealing with non-stationary signals which vary in frequency content over time. Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and Wavelet Transform are some of commonly used techniques for this purpose. STFT decomposes the signal into short time segments and applies Fourier Transform to each segment. In Wavelet Transform the signal is broken down according to multiple scales, allowing multi-resolution analysis.

2.1.2 RF SIGNAL MODULATIONS

RF signal modulation involves varying one or more properties of a carrier signal such as amplitude, frequency, or phase to transmit information. The main types of RF signal modulation include:

Amplitude Modulation: AM involves altering the amplitude of the carrier signal based on the message signal and is a basic type of RF signal modulation. AM, utilized

in AM radio transmission, allows for the distant transportation of audio by changing the amplitude of the radio waves. In AM, the frequency and phase of the carrier signal stay steady while only the amplitude varies. It is a commonly utilized, inexpensive technique in many different uses.

Frequency Modulation: Frequency modulation, contains variances of frequency of the carrier signal in accordance with the amplitude of the message signal. Here, the amplitude and phase remain constant. FM is widely used for FM radio broadcasting and other communication systems.

Phase Modulation: In phase modulation, the phase of the carrier signal is varied in proportion to the message signal, while the amplitude and frequency remain constant. PM is used in various digital modulation schemes and communication systems.

Quadrature Amplitude Modulation: QAM combines both amplitude and phase modulation. It involves varying both the amplitude and phase of the carrier signal to represent data. QAM is commonly used in digital television, cable modem, and other high-data-rate communication systems.

Frequency-Shift Keying: FSK is a form of frequency modulation where the carrier frequency is shifted between discrete values to represent binary data. It is used in digital communication systems such as modems and RFID.

Phase-Shift Keying: PSK involves varying the phase of the carrier signal to represent data. Common types of PSK include Binary Phase-Shift Keying (BPSK), Quadrature

Phase-Shift Keying (QPSK), and higher-order PSK schemes. PSK is widely used in wireless communication and satellite communication.

Amplitude-Shift Keying: ASK involves varying the amplitude of the carrier signal to represent binary data. The carrier frequency and phase remain constant. ASK is used in digital communication systems like RFID and optical communication.

Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing: OFDM is a multi-carrier modulation technique that divides the data into multiple closely spaced carrier frequencies, each modulated with a lower data rate. OFDM is used in modern communication systems such as Wi-Fi and LTE.

Minimum Shift Keying: MSK is a form of continuous-phase frequency-shift keying where the frequency changes are smooth, resulting in a constant envelope signal. MSK is used in digital communication systems like GSM.

These modulation techniques are chosen based on the requirements of the communication system, such as data rate, bandwidth efficiency, power efficiency, and resistance to noise and interference.

2.1.3 ENERGY SIGNALS AND POWER SIGNALS

Energy Signals

An energy signal is a signal that has finite energy over all time. The total energy of a signal $x(t)$ is defined as the integral of the square of its absolute value over time:

$$(2.1) \quad E = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \int_{-(T/2)}^{(T/2)} |x(t)|^2 dt$$

For discrete-time signals $x[n]$, the energy is given by:

$$(2.2) \quad E = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |x(n)|^2$$

An energy signal has finite energy but zero average power. Examples of energy signals include signals that exist for a limited duration of time or signals that decay to zero as time approaches infinity.

Power Signals

A power signal is a signal that has finite, non-zero power over all time. The average power of a signal $x(t)$ is defined as the limit of the time-averaged power over an infinite time interval:

$$(2.3) \quad P = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{-(T/2)}^{(T/2)} |x(t)|^2 dt$$

For discrete-time signals $x[n]$, the average power is given by:

$$(2.4) \quad P = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2N + 1} \sum_{n=-N}^N |x(n)|^2$$

A power signal has finite average power but infinite energy. Examples of power signals include periodic signals (like sine and cosine waves) and signals that do not decay to zero over time.

2.1.4 CORRELATION

Correlation is a fundamental concept in signal processing and statistics used to measure the relationship between two signals or datasets. It indicates how much one signal or

dataset resembles another and can be used to detect patterns, shifts, or similarities.

Here's an overview of the key concepts related to correlation:

1. **Auto-correlation:** Measures the similarity of a signal with a delayed version of itself over varying time lags. It is useful for detecting repeating patterns or periodicities in the signal.
2. **Cross-correlation:** Measures the similarity between two different signals as a function of the time-lag applied to one of them. It is used to find the time delay between two signals or to detect the presence of one signal within another.

2.1.5 SIGNAL ENTROPY

Signal entropy is a measure of the uncertainty or randomness of a signal. It is a concept in information theory that is used to quantify the amount of information contained in a signal. Higher entropy indicates more unpredictability and less redundancy, while lower entropy indicates more predictability and higher redundancy.

$$H(X) = - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} p(x) \log_b p(x) \quad (2.5)$$

,where $H(X)$ denotes the entropy of the random variable X and $p(x)$ represents the probability of a specific outcome x occurring.

Entropy is an often used in lossless data compression. It provides a theoretical limit on the minimum number of bits required to encode a signal without loss of information. Algorithms like Huffman coding and arithmetic coding are based on entropy. Other applications of entropy includes machine learning algorithms to select features,

building decision trees, and evaluating the uncertainty in predictions. For example, the Information Gain metric in decision trees is based on entropy.

2.2 FUNDAMENTALS OF SIGNAL ANALYSIS

The fundamentals of signal analysis covers a broad range of techniques and concepts that illustrates signal analysis for various applications, from communications to biomedical engineering.

2.2.1 FOURIER TRANSFORM

The Fourier Transform converts a signal from the time domain to the frequency domain, revealing the signal's frequency components. For a function $f(x)$ defined over the interval $-\infty < x < \infty$, the fourier transform is given by

$$\hat{f}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)e^{-i\omega x} dx \quad (2.6)$$

2.2.2 SHORT FOURIER TRANSFORM

The Short-Time Fourier Transform provides a time-frequency representation for analyzing signals with time-varying frequency content and it is given by:

$$(2.7) \quad X(\tau, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)w(t - \tau)e^{-i\omega t} dt$$

Where $w(t - \tau)$ is the window function.

2.2.3 POWER SPECTRAL DENSITY

The Power Spectral Density quantifies how the power of a signal $x(t)$ is distributed across different frequencies. PSD function is denoted by $S(\omega)$

$$S(\omega) = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|X(\omega)|^2}{\tau}$$

(2.8)

2.2.4 WAVELET TRANSFORM

The Wavelet Transform analyses signals at multiple scales, providing a detailed time-frequency representation. It is used to decompose a signal into its constituent components at various scales or resolutions. Unlike the Fourier transform, which represents a signal in terms of its frequency components, the wavelet transform provides both time and frequency localization, making it particularly useful for analyzing non-stationary signals whose frequency content varies over time.

The wavelet transform involves convolving the signal with a set of wavelets, which are functions that are localized in both time and frequency. These wavelets are generated by scaling and translating a single "mother wavelet." The result of the transform is a series of coefficients that represent the signal's content at different scales and positions.

There are two main type of wavelet transforms:

Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT): The CWT analyzes the signal over a continuous range of scales and positions, providing a highly detailed time-frequency representation. However, it can be computationally intensive and may produce a large amount of redundant data.

Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT): The DWT uses discrete scales and positions, typically chosen as powers of two. This version is more computationally efficient and often used in practical applications such as data compression and noise reduction.

The Continuous wavelet transform is given by

$$T(a, b) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \psi^* \left(\frac{t-b}{a} \right) dt \quad (2.9)$$

where $x(t)$ is the signal and Ψ is the wavelet function.

2.2.5 HILBERT TRANSFORM

The Hilbert Transform generates an analytic signal, which helps in extracting amplitude, phase, and instantaneous frequency information. It is a mathematical operator that transforms a real-valued signal into another real-valued signal in such a way that the transformed signal represents the original signal's phase information.

The Hilbert transform $\hat{x}(t)$ of a real-valued signal $x(t)$ is defined as:

$$\hat{x}(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x(\tau)}{t - \tau} d\tau \quad (2.10)$$

2.2.6 HILBERT- HUANG TRANSFORM

The Hilbert-Huang Transform (HHT) is a method for analyzing non-stationary and nonlinear signals. It combines the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD), which breaks a signal into Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs), with the Hilbert Transform to obtain the Hilbert Spectrum. This spectrum provides a time-frequency-energy representation that captures the signal's varying frequency content. It was developed by Norden E. Huang and his colleagues as an alternative to traditional methods like the Fourier Transform and Wavelet Transform. HHT stands out due to its adaptability and precision in dealing with complex signals.

Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) is the first step in the HHT process. It decomposes a complex signal into a set of simpler components known as Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs). These IMFs are characterized by having a number of extrema (local maxima and minima) that matches or nearly matches the number of zero-crossings, and a mean value of zero for the envelopes defined by the local maxima and minima. The EMD process is iterative and adaptive, meaning the decomposition is based on the data itself, which is particularly useful for analyzing non-linear and non-stationary signals.

After obtaining the IMFs, the second component, Hilbert Spectral Analysis (HSA), is applied. This involves the Hilbert Transform, which generates an analytic signal from each IMF. From this, the instantaneous amplitude and frequency can be derived, resulting in a time-frequency representation called the Hilbert Spectrum. This spectrum provides a highly localized and detailed view of the signal's frequency content, allowing for the analysis of signals with time-varying frequencies and amplitudes.

2.2.7 WIGNER – VILE DISTRIBUTION

The Wigner-Ville Distribution (WVD) is a time-frequency analysis tool that provides a joint representation of a signal in both the time and frequency domains. Named after Eugene Wigner and Jean-André Ville, the WVD is particularly useful for analyzing non-stationary signals, where the frequency content changes over time. Unlike traditional Fourier analysis, which only provides frequency information without time localization, the WVD offers a detailed view of how the frequency components of a signal evolve over time.

The Wigner-Ville Distribution (WVD) is an excellent technique for time-frequency (TF) analysis. It calculates the Fourier transform of the ambiguity function (AF), which is defined as

$$AF(\tau) = x(t + \tau/2)x^*(t - \tau/2) \quad (2.11)$$

The ambiguity function is a general representation of the signal's autocorrelation function. Unlike the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), the WVD is not affected by leakage effects, allowing it to offer superior spectral resolution.

2.3 FUNDAMENTALS OF NEURAL NETWORKS

Neural networks are a class of machine learning models inspired by the human brain, used for a variety of tasks including classification, regression, and pattern recognition.

2.3.1 BASIC IDEA BEHIND NEURAL NETWORKS

Neural networks are inspired by the structure and function of the human brain, specifically how neurons interact to process information. They consist of interconnected layers of nodes or neurons that work together to transform input data into output predictions or decisions. The process involves learning from data by adjusting connections (weights) between neurons based on the errors in predictions.

Photograph 2.1: John McCarthy: Computer scientist known as the father of AI

Core Components of Neural Networks

Neurons: The fundamental units of a neural network. Each neuron receives input, applies a mathematical function, and produces an output. Neurons are organized into layers, and each layer has a specific role in processing data.

Layers: Neural networks typically have three types of layers: The first layer that receives the raw data. Each neuron in this layer represents a feature or attribute of the data. Intermediate layers between the input and output layers. They perform complex transformations and capture patterns from the input data. The final layer that produces the network's predictions or decisions. Each neuron in this layer corresponds to a possible outcome or class.

Weights: Parameters that determine the strength of connections between neurons. They are adjusted during training to improve the network's accuracy.

Biases: Additional parameters that help shift the activation function and make the model more flexible.

Activation Functions: Mathematical functions applied to the neuron's output to introduce non-linearity into the network. Common functions include:

- **Sigmoid:** Maps values to a range between 0 and 1.
- **ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit):** Maps values to the maximum of 0 and the input value.
- **Tanh (Hyperbolic Tangent):** Maps values to a range between -1 and 1.

Figure 2.3 Sigmoid Function

Figure 2.4 ReLU Function

Figure 2.5 Tanh Function

2.3.2 PERCEPTRON

The perceptron, introduced by Frank Rosenblatt in 1958, is a foundational concept in the field of artificial intelligence and neural networks. As the simplest type of artificial neuron, it forms the basis for more complex neural network structures. Despite its simplicity, the perceptron embodies several key principles of machine learning and neural computation. A perceptron consists of several inputs, each assigned a weight, and a single output. The weights are numerical values that signify the importance or influence of the respective inputs. The perceptron also includes a bias term, which allows the activation threshold to be adjusted independently of the inputs. The core function of the perceptron involves computing a weighted sum of the inputs, adding the bias, and passing the result through an activation function. The standard activation

function used in a perceptron is a step function, which outputs either a 0 or 1 depending on whether the weighted sum is below or above a certain threshold.

Figure 2.6 Perceptron

$$\text{Output} = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b\right) \quad (2.12)$$

Eqn(2.12) represents the output of the perceptron, where b is the bias, w_i are weights and x_i are inputs.

2.3.3 BAYES CLASSIFIER

The Bayes Classifier is a statistical technique used in machine learning for classification tasks. It leverages Bayes' Theorem to make predictions based on probabilities. The Naive Bayes Classifier is a simplified version of the Bayes Classifier that assumes independence between features. It assumes that the presence or absence of a particular feature in a class is independent of the presence or absence of any other

feature. In other words, all features contribute independently to the probability that an object belongs to a certain class. Its goal is to calculate conditional probability for every possibilities.

$$\hat{y} = P(C_k) \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i | C_k) \tag{2.13}$$

Eqn(2.13) represents the final output for naive bayes classification, where $\hat{y}$ is the predicted class label.

Figure 2.7 Naive Bayes Classification

2.3.4 KNN

The KNN algorithm classifies data points based on the majority class of their K-nearest neighbours in the feature space. It's a non-parametric, instance-based learning method that doesn't explicitly build a model but rather makes decisions based on the proximity of data points.

Figure 2.8 K-nearest Neighbors

In the classification context, KNN works by finding the "k" closest training examples to a new data point and making predictions based on the majority class among these neighbours. The "k" is a user-defined constant, and selecting an appropriate value for "k" is crucial for the algorithm's performance. A small value of "k" can make the model sensitive to noise in the training data, while a large "k" may dilute the influence of closer neighbours.

2.3.5 LINEAR REGRESSION

Linear regression aims to find the best-fitting line through a set of data points. The line represents a relationship between the independent variables (features) and the dependent variable (target). The main goal is to predict the value of the target variable based on the values of the features.

2.3.6 LOGARITHMIC REGRESSION

Logarithmic regression is a type of regression analysis where the relationship between the independent variable x and the dependent variable y is modelled using a logarithmic function. This method is used when the data shows a trend that can be well-described by a logarithmic curve. It is particularly useful for data with exponential growth or decay patterns. Logarithmic regression models the relationship between two variables where one variable increases (or decreases) logarithmically with the other variable. The basic idea is to fit a logarithmic function to the data to better describe relationships where changes in the dependent variable slow down as the independent variable increases.

2.3.7 SIMPLE RNN

A Simple RNN is a type of artificial neural network where connections between nodes can create a cycle, allowing information to persist. Unlike traditional feedforward neural networks, RNNs can maintain a state or memory of past inputs through their recurrent connections. The core idea is that RNNs use the output from the previous step as part of the input for the next step, creating a loop-like structure that enables the network to learn from previous data points in a sequence.

2.3.8 CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a specialized type of neural network designed to process structured grid data, such as images. CNNs are particularly effective in capturing spatial hierarchies in data through the use of convolutional layers. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a class of deep learning models primarily used for processing data with grid-like topology, such as images. CNNs have revolutionized the field of computer vision, enabling breakthroughs in tasks like image classification, object detection, and image segmentation. Their architecture is designed to automatically and adaptively learn spatial hierarchies of features from input data, which has proven to be highly effective for visual recognition and analysis.

At the core of CNNs are the convolutional layers, which perform the convolution operation. This operation involves passing a small matrix called a filter or kernel over the input data to produce a feature map. The filter extracts local features by learning patterns such as edges, textures, and other fundamental elements from the data. These features are then combined at deeper layers to form higher-level representations, such as shapes and objects. The ability to learn hierarchical features makes CNNs particularly powerful in handling the variability and complexity present in image data.

Figure 2.9 Typical architecture of CNN

In Figure 2.9 A typical CNN architecture consists of several key components: convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. The convolutional layers are responsible for detecting and learning features. Pooling layers, often placed between convolutional layers, perform downsampling operations that reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps, thus decreasing the computational load and mitigating overfitting. Common types of pooling include max pooling, which selects the maximum value from a region of the feature map, and average pooling, which computes the average.

After several rounds of convolution and pooling, the network typically transitions to fully connected layers, which resemble the layers found in traditional neural networks. These layers interpret the high-level features learned by the convolutional and pooling layers to make predictions or classifications. For instance, in an image classification task, the final fully connected layer outputs a probability distribution over different categories, indicating the likelihood that the input image belongs to each class.

One of the remarkable aspects of CNNs is their ability to automatically learn filters during the training process, which eliminates the need for manual feature extraction. This capability is facilitated by using large datasets and powerful optimization algorithms like stochastic gradient descent. The network learns by adjusting the weights of the filters to minimize the difference between the predicted output and the actual labels, often using a loss function like cross-entropy for classification tasks. CNNs have several key properties that make them effective for image and video processing. Local connectivity, or the receptive field, ensures that each neuron in the convolutional layer is only connected to a small region of the input, preserving spatial

locality and reducing the number of parameters. This is particularly beneficial in handling high-dimensional data, as it keeps the computational requirements manageable. Weight sharing further reduces the number of parameters by using the same filter weights across different locations, enabling the network to detect the same feature in various parts of the image. The success of CNNs extends beyond image processing to various domains, including speech recognition, natural language processing, and even playing games. For example, in speech recognition, CNNs can learn to identify phonemes or words from spectrogram representations of audio signals. In natural language processing, they can capture patterns in text data, such as sentiment or topic, by treating text as a 1D grid of words or characters.

One of the most influential architectures in CNN history is the AlexNet, which won the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge in 2012. This network demonstrated the potential of deep learning for image classification, using eight layers and innovative techniques like ReLU activations and dropout to achieve unprecedented accuracy. Since then, many other architectures, such as VGG, ResNet, and Inception, have further advanced the field, each introducing new ideas and improvements in network design.

2.3.9 LTSM

LSTM networks are specialized RNN architectures that are capable of learning and remembering over long sequences of data. They achieve this by incorporating a memory cell and several gating mechanisms, which regulate the flow of information through the network. This structure enables LSTMs to maintain information for long periods, making them effective for tasks that require capturing long-term dependencies. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) architecture that are widely used in the field of deep learning, particularly for

tasks involving sequential data. Unlike standard feedforward neural networks, LSTMs have a built-in mechanism to retain information across long sequences, making them especially useful for tasks such as natural language processing, speech recognition, and time series forecasting.

The LSTM architecture was introduced by Sepp Hochreiter and Jürgen Schmidhuber in 1997 as a solution to the vanishing gradient problem that plagued traditional RNNs. In standard RNNs, the gradient of the loss function with respect to earlier layers diminishes exponentially as it is backpropagated through time. This results in the network's inability to learn long-range dependencies effectively, as the gradients become too small to make meaningful updates to the weights. LSTMs address this issue through a unique cell state and gating mechanism, enabling them to maintain and manipulate information over longer periods.

Architecture and Mechanism

The core component of an LSTM network is the memory cell, which acts as a repository for information. The cell state is regulated by three gates: the input gate, the forget gate, and the output gate. These gates control the flow of information into, out of, and through the cell, respectively.

Figure 2.10 Typical architecture of LSTM

The Figure 2.10 depicts the architecture of a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) cell, a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) used in deep learning for processing and predicting time series data. LSTM cells are designed to capture long-term dependencies and patterns in sequences, which standard RNNs struggle with due to issues like vanishing gradients.

1. Forget Gate: This gate determines which information from the cell state should be discarded. It takes the previous hidden state and the current input and passes them through a sigmoid function, producing a number between 0 and 1 for each component of the cell state. A value of 0 means "completely forget" while a value of 1 means "completely retain."

2. Input Gate: The input gate regulates the updating of the cell state with new information. It consists of two parts: a sigmoid layer that decides which values will be updated, and a tanh layer that creates a vector of new candidate values. The output from these two parts is combined to update the cell state.

3. Output Gate: The output gate decides the next hidden state, which also serves as the output of the LSTM cell. It filters the cell state through a sigmoid layer, and then multiplies the result by the tanh of the cell state, controlling how much of the cell state should influence the next hidden state.

One of the most significant advantages of LSTMs is their ability to learn long-term dependencies, which are important in many applications. For instance, in natural language processing, understanding the context of a word often requires knowledge of

words that appeared much earlier in the sentence. LSTMs are capable of capturing these dependencies, which makes them well-suited for tasks like language modeling, machine translation, and text generation.

In speech recognition, LSTMs can model temporal sequences of audio data, effectively capturing the nuances in speech over time. They are also extensively used in time series analysis, where understanding the trends and patterns over time is important. In the financial sector, LSTMs are employed for stock price prediction, and in the healthcare industry, they are used for patient monitoring and disease prediction. Despite their strengths, LSTMs are not without limitations. They can be computationally intensive, requiring more resources compared to simpler RNN architectures. Training LSTMs can also be slow, especially on large datasets, due to their complex structure and the need for careful tuning of hyperparameters.

Moreover, while LSTMs mitigate the vanishing gradient problem, they are not immune to it. For very long sequences, even LSTMs can struggle to maintain relevant information. This has led to the development of more advanced architectures like the Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) and Transformer models, which offer alternative solutions for handling long-range dependencies in sequential data.

2.3.10 GRU

GRU networks are a variant of RNNs that use gating mechanisms to control the flow of information through the network. They were introduced to reduce the complexity of LSTMs by combining the forget and input gates into a single update gate and by merging the memory cell and hidden state into a single entity.

2.3.11 HYBRID MODELS

Hybrid models are a combination of two or more models to undertake complex tasks. These models are required when there is a need for specialized operation. Hybrid models have the ability to combine the features of two or more models into one. Our study is also based on hybrid model which is a combination of CNN and LSTM.

Table 2.1 Neural Networks

Model Type	Architecture
Feed Forward Network	Layers of neurons with unidirectional connections
Convolutional Neural Network	Layers with feedback loops, sequences of data
Recurrent Neural Network	Layers with feedback loops, sequences of data
Long Short Term Memory	Specialized RNN with memory cells
Gated Recurrent Network	Simplified LSTM with fewer parameters
Generative Adversarial Network	Two neural networks (generator and discriminator) in adversarial setup
Transformer	Attention mechanism, parallel processing
Graph Neural Network	Nodes and edges representing graph data

CHAPTER 3

Neural Network Terminologies

This chapter covers the commonly used terminologies in neural networks. It provides a comprehensive overview of key concepts and terms that are fundamental to understanding neural networks and their operations. This includes terms such as Accuracy, training, Epochs etc., which is essential for understanding further chapters.

3.1 METRICS OF PERFORMANCE

Performance metrics help quantify how well a machine learning model performs its intended task. Whether it's classifying images, predicting future sales, or grouping similar data points, metrics provide a clear measure of the model's effectiveness. They translate complex predictions into understandable values, such as accuracy or error rates, that reflect how well the model achieves its goals.

3.2 TRAINING

Training a neural network involves a series of systematic steps to adjust the network's weights and biases so that it can effectively learn from data and make accurate predictions.

3.3 ACCURACY

Accuracy measures the proportion of correct predictions among all predictions made. It is calculated by dividing the number of correct predictions by the total number of predictions. While accuracy is straightforward, it can be misleading in imbalanced datasets where the majority class might dominate the results.

3.4 LOSS FUNCTION

A loss function, also known as a cost function, measures the difference between the predicted values and the actual target values in a machine learning model. It quantifies how well or poorly the model is performing. By minimizing the loss function during training, the model's predictions get closer to the actual values. Common loss functions include Mean Squared Error for regression tasks and Cross-Entropy Loss for

classification tasks. The choice of loss function depends on the specific problem and the nature of the output.

3.5 ACTIVATION FUNCTION

An activation function is a mathematical function applied to the output of a neural network layer. It introduces non-linearity into the model, allowing it to learn complex patterns and representations. Without activation functions, neural networks would only be able to model linear relationships. Common activation functions include the Sigmoid, Tanh, and Rectified Linear Unit. Each has its characteristics and use cases, with ReLU being widely used due to its simplicity and effectiveness in reducing the vanishing gradient problem. The choice of activation function can significantly impact the model's performance and learning dynamics.

3.6 CONFUSION MATRIX

A confusion matrix is a table that shows the number of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. It provides a detailed view of the model's performance and helps in calculating other metrics. It provides a detailed breakdown of the model's predictions compared to the actual labels, allowing for a clear visualization of where the model is making errors. Understanding and interpreting a confusion matrix is important for assessing the effectiveness of a classifier and identifying areas for improvement.

3.7 EPOCHS

An epoch is a single iteration through the entire training dataset. During one epoch, the neural network processes each example in the dataset once. This involves performing

forward propagation to make predictions, calculating the loss, and updating the model's weights through backpropagation.

3.8 FAULT TOLERANCE

Fault tolerance refers to a system's ability to continue operating properly in the event of the failure of some of its components.

3.9 COMPLEXITY REGULARISATIONS

Complexity regularization is a technique used in machine learning and statistical modelling to prevent overfitting by penalizing models with excessive complexity. Overfitting occurs when a model learns not only the underlying pattern in the training data but also the noise, leading to poor generalization on unseen data. Regularization techniques add constraints or penalties to the loss function to discourage overly complex models, thereby improving their generalization capability.

3.10 NETWORK PRUNING

Network pruning is a technique used in deep learning to reduce the size and complexity of neural networks without significantly compromising their performance. It involves removing redundant or less important parameters (such as weights and neurons) from the network. Pruning can lead to more efficient models that require less memory and computational power, making them suitable for deployment in resource-constrained environments like mobile devices and edge computing.

CHAPTER 4

Data Preprocessing

Raw data, as it is initially gathered, is often marred by inconsistencies, missing values, and noise. Transforming this raw data into a standardised structured format is important for proper implementation of neural network. This chapter deals with the methods implemented for data preprocessing.

4.1 FORMATS OF DATASETS

Table 4.1 File types in Data Science

File Type	Characteristics	Typical use case
CSV	Plain text, tabular data	Datasets
Excel	Spreadsheet format	Data manipulating and reporting
JSON	Text format	Data Interchange, Web APIs
XML	Text format	Data exchange
HDF5	Binary format	Large Scale data storage
Parquet	Columnar storage	Big Data processing
SQL	Text format	Database Management
TXT	Plain text	Logs
YAML	Text format	Configuration Files
Pickle	Binary format	Saving Python Objects

In data science, various file types are employed to handle different aspects of data storage, management, and analysis. CSV and Excel files are often used for simple data storage and manipulation, while JSON and XML are preferred for hierarchical data and data exchange. HDF5 and Parquet are used for large-scale data storage and processing, and SQL files manage relational database tasks. TXT files serve for basic text storage, YAML for human-readable configurations, and Pickle files for Python object serialization. Each file type has its own strengths and is chosen based on the specific requirements of the data science tasks at hand.

HDF5

An HDF5 file (Hierarchical Data Format version 5) is a file format and set of tools for managing complex data. It supports the creation, access, and sharing of scientific data in a versatile and efficient way. HDF5 files can store large amounts of data, support fast I/O, and facilitate the organization of data in a hierarchical structure.

CSV

A CSV (Comma-Separated Values) file is a simple text file that stores tabular data. Each line in the file corresponds to a row in the table, and each value in the row is separated by a comma. CSV files are commonly used for exchanging data between different applications, such as spreadsheets and databases, because of their simplicity and wide support.

4.2 MISSING VALUES

Missing data inside datasets can result from a variety of sources such as sensor malfunctions, data entry errors, or simply unrecorded information. To address this, several strategies are employed. One approach is to eliminate records with missing values, though this can lead to a reduction in dataset size. For our datasets no such missing values were found.

4.3 DATA SAMPLING

Sampling is essential for several reasons. Firstly, it is often impractical or impossible to collect data from an entire population due to constraints such as time, cost, and resources. Sampling provides a feasible alternative that allows researchers to gather and analyze data efficiently. Secondly, a well-chosen sample can provide accurate estimates of population parameters, enabling researchers to make generalizations about the population. Finally, sampling helps in reducing the volume of data to a manageable size, making analysis more straightforward and less resource-intensive.

4.4 DATA SEGMENTATION

Data Segmentation involves dividing a dataset into distinct, meaningful segments or groups based on certain criteria. This process allows analysts to gain deeper insights,

tailor strategies to specific subgroups, and enhance the effectiveness of their analyses and models. The primary objective of data segmentation is to identify and create homogenous subgroups within a dataset, where each subgroup exhibits similar characteristics or behaviours.

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4.5 PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

PCA is a dimensionality reduction technique that aims to simplify data without losing significant information. It achieves this by identifying the most important features in a dataset and transforming them into a new set of variables called principal components. These components capture the maximum variance in the data, making it easier to visualize, analyze, and interpret. The fundamental idea behind PCA is to find a new coordinate system for the data where the greatest variance is captured along the first axis, the second greatest variance along the second axis, and so on. This is done by creating a set of orthogonal (uncorrelated) axes, known as principal components, that represent the directions of maximum variance in the data. The first principal component captures the largest amount of variance, the second principal component captures the second largest amount of variance orthogonal to the first, and so forth.

CHAPTER 5

Feature Extraction Methods

This chapter focuses on feature engineering, exploring various methods used in feature extraction and their distinct advantages and applications. We will cover the concepts behind these methods and their practical uses. A feature can have both a conceptual and a practical meaning, and features are sometimes referred to as filters. In the context of neural networks, data passed through any set of filters produces output. These filters, often represented as $[4 \times 4]$ or $[16 \times 16]$ matrices, are learned by the system over multiple epochs. Feature extraction is the process of transforming raw data into a set of features that can be effectively utilized by machine learning models. These features can be derived from various types of data, including time series, images, text, and more.

5.1 TIME DOMAIN METHODS

These methods focus on the time-dependent characteristics of signals, making them essential for understanding temporal variations, amplitude changes, and waveform shapes. By working directly with the original time-domain representation, these methods provide insights into the behaviour of signals that are important for applications such as audio processing, communications, and control systems. One of the simplest and most common time domain methods is time-domain analysis, where a signal's properties are examined directly from its waveform. This approach involves observing features such as amplitude, duration, and periodicity, which can provide valuable information about the signal's characteristics. For example, in audio processing, analyzing the waveform can help identify different sounds, such as speech, music, or noise, based on their distinct time-domain patterns. Another important time domain method is convolution, a mathematical operation that combines two signals to produce a third signal, representing the effect of one signal on the other.

Convolution is widely used in systems analysis and filter design, where it helps to determine the output of a system given its impulse response and input signal. This technique is fundamental in areas like image processing, where convolution filters are used for tasks such as edge detection and blurring.

Correlation is another key time domain method, used to measure the similarity between two signals as a function of time lag. This technique can identify time delays or shifts between signals, making it useful in applications like echo detection and synchronization in communications. Auto-correlation, a specific form of correlation where a signal is

correlated with itself, is used to detect repeating patterns or periodicities within the signal, such as identifying the fundamental frequency in musical tones.

5.2 TRANSFORM BASED METHODS

Transform-based methods are techniques in signal processing, used to convert signals from one domain to another, often to facilitate analysis, interpretation, or manipulation. These methods are important in understanding the characteristics of signals, such as their frequency content or phase information, which may not be easily discernible in their original form. Key examples of transform-based methods include Fourier transforms, Hilbert transforms, and several others, each serving specific purposes in different applications.

The Fourier Transform is one of the most widely used transform-based methods. It converts a time-domain signal into its frequency-domain representation, revealing the various frequency components that make up the signal. This transformation is essential for analyzing the spectral content of signals, identifying dominant frequencies, and understanding the signal's behaviour in the frequency domain. The Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and its fast implementation, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), are commonly used in digital signal processing to efficiently compute this transformation for discrete signals. The Fourier Transform is particularly valuable in applications such as audio signal processing, where it helps in identifying pitch and harmonics, and in communications, where it is used for modulation and demodulation processes.

The Hilbert Transform is another important transform-based method, often used to derive the analytic signal from a real-valued signal. The analytic signal is a complex-

valued representation that includes both the original signal and its Hilbert Transform as the imaginary part. This transformation is instrumental in calculating the instantaneous amplitude and phase of a signal, providing insights into its modulation characteristics. The Hilbert Transform is widely used in communications for demodulating amplitude-modulated (AM) signals and in biomedical engineering for analyzing the phase and amplitude variations in physiological signals, such as electrocardiograms (ECGs) and electroencephalograms (EEGs).

Wavelet Transforms are another class of transform-based methods that provide a time-frequency representation of a signal. Unlike the Fourier Transform, which represents a signal entirely in the frequency domain, the Wavelet Transform retains both time and frequency information, allowing for the analysis of non-stationary signals—those whose spectral characteristics change over time. This makes wavelet analysis particularly useful in applications like image compression, where localized features such as edges are important, and in seismic signal analysis, where identifying transient events is important.

The Z-Transform is a mathematical transformation used in discrete-time signal processing. It maps a discrete-time signal into the complex frequency domain, making it easier to analyze and design digital filters and control systems. The Z-Transform is particularly useful for studying the stability and frequency response of discrete-time systems.

Another significant transform is the Laplace Transform, which is used to analyze continuous-time systems and signals. It transforms a time-domain function into a complex frequency domain, providing a comprehensive view of the system's behavior,

including stability and transient responses. The Laplace Transform is widely used in control engineering, physics, and other fields requiring the analysis of dynamic systems.

5.3 SIGNAL DECOMPOSITION METHODS

Signal decompositions involve dividing the signal into two or more parts to facilitate better analysis. Signal decomposition methods are techniques used in signal processing to break down a complex signal into simpler components. This decomposition facilitates better analysis, interpretation, and manipulation of the signal, making it easier to extract meaningful information or to enhance certain features. By dividing a signal into its constituent parts, we can analyze these components separately, which can be particularly useful in fields such as audio processing, biomedical signal analysis, and communications. One of the most common signal decomposition techniques is Wavelet Transform, which provides a time-frequency representation of a signal. Unlike the Fourier Transform, which provides only frequency information, the Wavelet Transform can capture both time and frequency characteristics simultaneously. This makes it particularly useful for analyzing signals with non-stationary or transient features, such as sudden bursts or localized changes. In this method, a signal is decomposed into a series of wavelets, which are localized in both time and frequency, allowing for a detailed examination of the signal's structure at different scales. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is another decomposition technique, often used in data analysis and signal processing to reduce dimensionality and extract essential features. PCA transforms the original signal into a set of orthogonal components, known as principal components, which capture the maximum variance in the data. By focusing on the most significant components, PCA can simplify the analysis, reduce noise, and highlight the most important features of the signal. Empirical Mode Decomposition is a technique

used primarily for analyzing non-linear and non-stationary signals. It decomposes a signal into a set of intrinsic mode functions, which represent simple oscillatory modes with varying frequencies. This method is particularly useful in biomedical signal processing, such as analyzing electroencephalograms or electrocardiograms, where the signal components can have complex, non-linear interactions. Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) is another decomposition method that factorizes a matrix representing the signal into three components: a matrix of singular vectors, a diagonal matrix of singular values, and another matrix of singular vectors. This decomposition can be used to extract the most significant features from a signal, reduce noise, or perform tasks such as image compression. Signal decomposition methods are important in a wide range of applications. In audio processing, these techniques can be used to separate different musical instruments or voices in a recording, enhance specific components, or reduce background noise.

5.4 ENVELOP BASED METHODS

Envelope-based methods are a class of techniques in signal processing that focus on extracting the envelope of a signal. The envelope of a signal represents its amplitude variations over time, providing valuable information about the signal's structure and characteristics. These methods are particularly useful in applications such as communications, audio signal processing, and biomedical signal analysis, where understanding the amplitude variations can be important for tasks like demodulation, feature extraction, and noise reduction. The concept of an envelope in signal processing refers to a smooth curve that outlines the extremes of a waveform. This envelope can be visualized as a smooth line that follows the peaks and troughs of the signal, essentially capturing the amplitude variations without being affected by the high-

frequency components. Envelope-based methods aim to isolate this aspect of the signal, filtering out the high-frequency oscillations and leaving a representation that highlights the overall amplitude changes. One common approach in envelope-based methods is the use of analytic signals and the Hilbert transform. An analytic signal is a complex-valued signal that has no negative frequency components, and it can be constructed from a real-valued signal using the Hilbert transform. The Hilbert transform provides the imaginary part of the analytic signal, while the original signal provides the real part. The envelope of the signal can then be obtained by computing the magnitude of this analytic signal, which effectively captures the amplitude variations over time. Another technique used in envelope detection is the use of filters, such as low-pass filters, to smooth out the signal and retain only the envelope information. In this approach, the original signal is passed through a low-pass filter that removes high-frequency components, leaving a signal that represents the envelope. This method is particularly useful in applications where the signal contains a mix of high-frequency and low-frequency components, and the goal is to focus on the slower variations. Envelope-based methods are widely used in various fields. In communication systems, for example, these methods are used in amplitude modulation demodulation, where the goal is to recover the original message signal from the modulated carrier. The envelope of the modulated signal contains the information about the message, and extracting this envelope allows for the recovery of the transmitted data.

In audio signal processing, envelope detection can be used for tasks such as dynamic range compression, where the goal is to reduce the volume differences between the loud and quiet parts of a signal. By analyzing the envelope, the system can apply appropriate gain adjustments to smooth out these variations

CHAPTER 6

Neural Network Lifecycle

This chapter deals with the lifecycle process of neural network providing the all-important information related to it. This portion of research work will help in gaining valuable insights into the background cycles and mechanism between hidden layers.

The lifecycle of a neural network begins with problem definition, where the specific problem to be solved is identified, along with the objectives and constraints of the project. This is followed by data collection and preprocessing, which involves gathering the necessary data, cleaning it, handling missing values, and transforming it into a suitable format for the neural network. The data is then split into training, validation, and test sets.

Next is model selection and design. Here, the appropriate neural network architecture is chosen based on the nature of the problem. The configuration of the network, including the number of layers, types of layers, and the number of neurons per layer, is determined. Hyperparameter such as learning rate, batch size, and activation functions are also selected.

The training phase involves defining a loss function that the network will aim to minimize and choosing an optimization algorithm to update the model parameters. The model is trained on the training data while its performance is monitored on the validation set to prevent overfitting. Regularization techniques like dropout and L1/L2 regularization may be applied to improve generalization. After training, the model is evaluated using performance metrics relevant to the problem, such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score.

The model's performance is assessed on both the validation and test sets, and an error analysis is conducted to identify areas for improvement. The model may be compared

to other models to select the best-performing one. Finally, the model is deployed to a production environment where it can be used to make predictions on new data.

Post-deployment, the model is monitored for performance degradation over time, and maintenance tasks such as retraining with new data or adjusting for concept drift are performed to ensure the model remains effective.

Figure 6.1 AI Life cycle

In Figure 1.1 the AI lifecycle is shown, beginning with problem definition and ending with deployment. In between there are various cycles namely data acquisition, model definition, model training and model evaluation with refinement.

CHAPTER 7

Methodology and Approach

This chapter covers approaches used in obtaining the results. It also outlines a number of steps taken to ensure results are properly recorded. The methodology section starts with defining the model and then leads to training the neural network. Finally validation tests are simulated to get the performance of model developed.

Theoretical framework

A theoretical framework is a structure that guides research by providing a clear, organized way to understand and interpret the study's findings. It consists of theories, concepts, and propositions that form a coherent foundation for analyzing a research problem. Theoretical frameworks help researchers identify and define the variables relevant to their study, establish relationships between those variables, and offer explanations for observed phenomena.

Flowchart of framework

7.1 DATASET AND PREPROCESSING

A dataset is a collection of data organized in a structured format, usually represented as a table with rows and columns where each row corresponds to a data instance or record, and each column represents a feature or attribute. Datasets can come in various forms, including spreadsheets, CSV files, SQL databases, and JSON files. They serve as the raw material from which insights are derived, models are built, and predictions are made. The quality and characteristics of the dataset significantly influence the effectiveness of the analysis or machine learning model.

Preprocessing is the series of techniques and methods used to clean, transform, and organize raw data into a format suitable for analysis or model building. It involves several critical steps aimed at improving the quality of the data and making it compatible with analytical methods or algorithms. The initial step in preprocessing is data collection, where data is gathered from various sources such as surveys, databases, APIs, web scraping, or sensors. Once collected, the data often requires cleaning to

handle issues like missing values, duplicate records, errors, or outliers. This involves methods for filling in or imputing missing values, removing duplicates, correcting inaccuracies, and addressing outliers that may affect the analysis.

Following data cleaning, the next step is data transformation, which involves converting the data into a suitable format for analysis or modelling. This includes normalizing or scaling data to bring different features to a common range, encoding categorical variables into numerical formats through techniques like one-hot encoding or label encoding, and performing feature engineering to create new features that can improve model performance. Transformation also encompasses aggregation methods to summarize data and make it more manageable.

Data integration is another essential step where data from different sources is combined to create a unified dataset. This process might involve merging datasets or joining tables using operations like inner join, outer join, or cross join to integrate related data. Data reduction techniques are also applied to reduce the volume of data while maintaining its integrity. This can involve dimensionality reduction methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce the number of features or data sampling techniques to select a representative subset of the data.

The final stage of preprocessing is data splitting, where the dataset is divided into subsets for training, validation, and testing. The training set is used to build the model, the validation set is used to tune Hyperparameter and assess model performance during training, and the test set is used to evaluate the model's performance on new, unseen data.

7.2 MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed model is CNN-LSTM, but first we discuss the CNN model that will be implemented.

7.2.1 CNN Model

Architecture:

Figure 7.1 Architecture of CNN

Figure 7.1 shows the neural network architecture with two Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), followed by a concatenation layer and a dense layer.

1. CNN 1 and CNN 2:

These two CNNs have same configurations (kernel sizes, numbers of filters, and input types). They extract features from the input data through convolutional layers, they also

contain pooling layers. The two inputs are In phase component of signal and quadrature component.

Each CNN outputs a feature map, which is a representation of the input data transformed by the learned filters.

2. Concatenation (Concat) Layer:

The outputs from CNN 1 and CNN 2 are concatenated along a specified axis. This operation combines the feature maps from both CNNs into a single tensor. The concatenated tensor now contains combined information extracted by both CNNs.

3. Dense Layer:

The concatenated features are passed through a dense (fully connected) layer. This layer helps in learning complex patterns and relationships in the data. It consists of neurons that apply a linear transformation followed by an activation function (such as ReLU, sigmoid, etc.) to the input features.

4. Output Layer with One-Hot Encoding:

The output layer uses one-hot encoding to represent the final predictions. In classification tasks, this is common where each neuron in the output layer corresponds to a different class. The activation function for this layer is typically softmax for multi-class classification, which outputs probabilities for each class.

7.2.2 CNN-LSTM Model

Architecture:

Figure 7.2 Architecture of CNN-LSTM

Figure 7.2 shows the architecture of CNN-LSTM. The model is developed as shown in architecture.

1. CNN 1 and CNN 2:

These two Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) process different aspects of the input data, extracting features through convolutional layers and with pooling layers. The CNNs are similar in their configurations, such as the number of layers, filter sizes, and types of input data they handle.

1. Concatenation (Concat) Layer:

The outputs from CNN 1 and CNN 2 are concatenated along a specified axis. This concatenation merges the feature maps produced by both CNNs into a single tensor, combining the extracted features into a unified representation.

2. LSTM Layer:

- The concatenated feature map is passed through a LSTM layer. LSTMs are a type of RNN well-suited for handling sequential data and learning temporal dependencies. The LSTM layer processes the input sequence and retains information over time, making it useful for tasks where the order of the data matters, such as time series analysis or natural language processing.

3. Output Layer with One-Hot Encoding:

- The final output layer produces predictions using one-hot encoding. In a classification setting, this typically involves a softmax activation function that assigns probabilities to each class. The highest probability indicates the predicted class.

This architecture combines feature extraction using CNNs with temporal sequence modelling using LSTMs. It's particularly useful in scenarios where the data has both spatial and temporal dimensions, such as video classification, audio analysis, or any time-dependent data. The CNNs capture spatial features, while the LSTM captures temporal patterns and dependencies.

CHAPTER 8

Model Evaluation

This chapter discusses in brief the hybrid CNN-LSTM models performance.

So, Did it worked?

Evaluation

The CNN-LSTM model demonstrated an improvement in both training and validation metrics over the course of 25 epochs. Starting with an initial training accuracy of 44.70% and a loss of 1.2316, the model quickly progressed to a final accuracy of 93.82% with a corresponding loss of 0.1417. The validation accuracy, a critical measure of the model's ability to generalize to unseen data, also improved steadily, reaching 91.39% by the end of training. Alongside the increasing accuracy, the validation loss decreased from 0.5934 in the first epoch to 0.2028 in the final epoch, indicating a reduction in the difference between predicted and actual outcomes. This consistent improvement in both training and validation metrics suggested that the model effectively learned and adapted to the patterns in the data without significant overfitting. The early stopping and model check-pointing techniques ensured that the best-performing model was retained in every epochs preventing overtraining. Further details of results are discussed in chapter 9 of this dissertation.

CHAPTER 9

Results and Discussions

In this chapter findings of the research is discussed. It starts with the outcomes of simulations outputs of CNN model and its performance analysis. Then the simulated outputs of CNN-LSTM model is discussed showing its improvement over the CNN.

Results of CNN model:

Figure 9.1 Accuracy vs Epochs of CNN

Figure 9.2 Loss vs Epochs of CNN

Figure 9.3 Confusion Matrix of CNN

CNN model's performance comments

Initial Performance (Epoch 1):

- Training Accuracy: 58.45%
- Training Loss: 0.8879
- Validation Accuracy: 77.54%
- Validation Loss: 0.5018

At the start, the model had moderate performance, with room for improvement.

Early Improvement (Epochs 2-4):

The model demonstrated significant gains in accuracy and reductions in loss:

Epoch 2: Training accuracy increased to 76.71%, and validation accuracy improved to 78.73%.

Epoch 3: Training accuracy reached 79.40%, with validation accuracy climbing to 81.33%.

Epoch 4: Training accuracy further improved to 82.48%, but validation accuracy slightly dropped to 81.32%.

The consistent decrease in training loss suggests effective learning, though minor fluctuations in validation accuracy indicate potential issues with overfitting or data variability.

Continued Training (Epochs 5-12):

The model continued to enhance its performance:

By Epoch 5, training accuracy was 84.18%, and validation accuracy rose to 83.90%.

Epoch 6: Training accuracy improved to 85.45%, with validation accuracy reaching 86.90%.

Epoch 7-8: Training accuracy increased to 87.32% and then 88.89%, with validation accuracy also improving to 87.35% and 87.59%, respectively.

Training loss decreased steadily, indicating improved model fitting, while validation accuracy remained relatively stable with minor fluctuations, suggesting good generalization.

Final Epochs (Epochs 13-15):

The model reached its highest training accuracy of 97.71% by epoch 15, but validation accuracy slightly decreased to 87.31%.

The validation loss increased slightly to 0.4405 by the final epoch, indicating some potential overfitting or changes in validation data characteristics.

After restoring the model, the final accuracy was 87.31% on the test dataset, demonstrating good performance overall.

The CNN model showed decent learning progress and reflected increase in training and validation accuracies, along with decreasing training loss. The final model achieved good training accuracy and maintained good validation performance, indicating effective generalization. However, the final epochs suggest an increase in validation loss and reduction in validation accuracy, which suggests over-fitting.

Results of CNN-LSTM model:

Figure 9.4 Loss vs Epochs of CNN-LSTM

Figure 9.5 Accuracy vs Epochs of CNN-LSTM

Figure 9.6 Confusion Matrix of CNN-LSTM

CNN-LSTM Performance comments

The CNN-LSTM model, which combines Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, was trained and evaluated over 25 epochs. The following was the performance of the model:

Initial Performance (Epoch 1):

- Training Accuracy: 0.4470
- Training Loss: 1.2316
- Validation Accuracy: 0.7356
- Validation Loss: 0.5934

The model started with a relatively low accuracy, typical for early training stages, indicating it had room for learning and optimization.

Early Improvement (Epochs 2-4):

- The model showed significant improvement in both training and validation accuracy, reaching:
 - Epoch 2: Training accuracy of 0.7273 and validation accuracy of 0.6993.
 - Epoch 3: Training accuracy of 0.7703 and validation accuracy of 0.7889.
 - Epoch 4: Training accuracy of 0.7814 and validation accuracy of 0.7986.
- Loss values also decreased consistently, indicating better model fitting and learning of the underlying patterns in the data.

Continued Training (Epochs 5-12):

- The model continued to improve, with training accuracy reaching 0.8686 by epoch 12. Validation accuracy also improved, though it fluctuated slightly, reaching up to 0.8814 by epoch 14.
- Notably, there were slight drops in validation accuracy during this period, suggesting potential over-fitting or noise in the validation data.

Final Epochs (Epochs 13-25):

- The model achieved its highest training accuracy of 0.9382 by the final epoch, with a validation accuracy of 0.9139.
- The validation loss reached a final value of 0.2028, indicating good generalization to the validation set.

After restoring the model, the final accuracy was recorded at 91.39%, reflecting a better performance than CNN counter-part on the test dataset.

The CNN-LSTM model demonstrated a better capacity to learn and generalize from the data, as indicated by the steady increase in accuracy and decrease in loss values. The combination of CNNs and LSTMs contributed to the model's ability to capture both spatial and temporal features, which are important in signal processing tasks. The use of checkpoints to save the best model weights based on validation performance also helped in maintaining the best-performing model throughout the training process.

CHAPTER 10

Conclusion

It was observed that the hybrid CNN-LSTM model demonstrated better capabilities than CNN model. The CNN-LSTM model had improved learning curve, achieving better accuracy and a consistent reduction in loss throughout the training process. With a final training accuracy of 93.82% and a validation accuracy of 91.39%, the model had good generalization capabilities to new data. The improvement in performance metrics was seen in the hybrid CNN-LSTM. These key points affirm the model's suitability for its intended application that is ensuring accurate and dependable predictions in proper signal analysis.

Scope for future work

The field of communication has been at the forefront of technological innovation, with signal analysis playing a critical role in the transmission, processing, and interpretation of data. In recent years, the advent of neural networks has revolutionized signal analysis, opening up new possibilities for enhancing communication systems. As we look to the future, the scope for further advancements in this area is vast, driven by ongoing research and technological developments.

One of the most promising avenues for future work is the development of advanced neural network architectures specifically tailored for signal analysis in communication systems. Deep learning models, such as CNNs and RNNs, have already shown great

promise in handling various signal processing tasks, from modulation recognition to noise reduction. However, newer architectures, such as transformers, which have revolutionized natural language processing, could bring similar advancements to signal processing. These models can capture long-range dependencies and intricate patterns in signals, potentially leading to more efficient and accurate communication systems.

Another emerging area is the application of graph neural networks (GNNs) in communication. GNNs are particularly well-suited for analyzing structured data, making them ideal for understanding the relationships between different components in communication networks. For instance, GNNs can be used to optimize routing protocols, detect anomalies in network traffic, and improve the efficiency of data transmission. This capability is especially relevant as networks become more complex with the proliferation of devices in the Internet of Things (IoT) era.

The real-time processing of communication signals is another critical area where neural networks can make significant contributions. As communication networks evolve to support applications like autonomous vehicles, virtual reality, and real-time streaming, the need for instantaneous signal processing has become paramount. Neural networks can be deployed on specialized hardware, such as graphics processing units (GPUs) and field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAs), to accelerate the processing of complex signals. This, coupled with advancements in edge computing, allows for signal processing to occur closer to the data source, reducing latency and improving overall system responsiveness.

Interpretability and explainability of neural network models are becoming increasingly important, especially in fields like telecommunications, where understanding the

decision-making process is important. As neural networks become more integrated into communication systems, there is a growing need to ensure that these models can be trusted and that their outputs can be interpreted by human operators. This is particularly important in critical applications such as emergency response communications, where the reliability and transparency of the system are important. Future research can focus on developing techniques to explain how neural networks process and interpret signal data, making them more transparent and trustworthy.

Data efficiency and transfer learning are also key areas for future research in neural network-based signal analysis. Traditionally, neural networks require vast amounts of data to perform effectively, which can be a limitation in communication systems where labelled data is scarce. However, advancements in short-term learning and semi-supervised learning can help neural networks learn from limited data, making them more adaptable and efficient. Additionally, transfer learning allows neural networks trained on one type of signal data to be adapted to another, reducing the need for extensive retraining and enabling faster deployment in new communication scenarios.

In terms of practical applications, neural networks hold potential for enhancing security and robustness in communication systems. As cyber threats become more sophisticated, there is a growing need for advanced techniques to detect and mitigate these threats. Neural networks can be employed to analyze network traffic, identify malicious activities, and implement adaptive security measures. Furthermore, techniques such as adversarial training can be used to make neural networks more robust against attempts to deceive them with misleading or corrupted signals. Also ethical implications of using neural networks in communication signal analysis cannot be overlooked. As these technologies become more pervasive, concerns about bias,

fairness, and privacy are increasingly coming to the forefront. Ensuring that neural networks do not perpetuate biases present in training data and developing privacy-preserving techniques are important steps toward building ethical and equitable communication systems. This includes exploring federated learning, where models are trained across decentralized devices without sharing sensitive data, thus preserving user privacy.

Photograph 10.1: Global INDIAai Summit 2024

The future of signal analysis in communication using neural networks is promising, with opportunities for innovation and improvement. As we continue to explore and develop new neural network architectures, improve real-time processing capabilities, and address ethical concerns, the research development can bring forward new potentials in communication systems.

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APPENDIX-A

Additional Tables

A.1

Fourier series table

	$x(t)$	a_k or the Fourier series expansion
a)	$\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(t - nT)$	$a_k = \frac{1}{T}$, all k
b)	1	$(a_0 = 1, a_k = 0 \text{ otherwise}), \quad \forall T_0 > 0$
c)	$e^{j\Omega_o t}$	$a_1 = 1, a_k = 0 \text{ otherwise}$
d)	$\cos \Omega_o t$	$a_1 = a_{-1} = \frac{1}{2}, a_k = 0 \text{ otherwise}$
e)	$\sin \Omega_o t$	$a_1 = -a_{-1} = \frac{1}{2j}, a_k = 0 \text{ otherwise}$
f)	$\begin{cases} 1, & t < T_1 \\ 0, & T_1 < t \leq \frac{T_o}{2} \end{cases}$ period T_0	$a_k = \frac{\Omega_o T_1}{\pi} \text{sinc} \frac{k\Omega_o T_1}{\pi} = \frac{\sin k\Omega_o T_1}{k\pi}$
g)	$\begin{cases} 1, & 0 < t < \pi \\ -1, & -\pi < t < 0 \end{cases}$	$\frac{4}{\pi} \left(\frac{\sin t}{1} + \frac{\sin 3t}{3} + \frac{\sin 5t}{5} + \dots \right)$
h)	$ t = \begin{cases} t, & 0 < t < \pi \\ -t, & -\pi < t < 0 \end{cases}$	$\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{4}{\pi} \left(\frac{\cos t}{1^2} + \frac{\cos 3t}{3^2} + \frac{\cos 5t}{5^2} + \dots \right)$
i)	$t, \quad -\pi < t < \pi$	$2 \left(\frac{\sin t}{1} - \frac{\sin 2t}{2} + \frac{\sin 3t}{3} - \dots \right)$
j)	$t, \quad 0 < t < 2\pi$	$\pi - 2 \left(\frac{\sin t}{1} + \frac{\sin 2t}{2} + \frac{\sin 3t}{3} + \dots \right)$
k)	$ \sin t , \quad -\pi < t < \pi$	$\frac{2}{\pi} - \frac{4}{\pi} \left(\frac{\cos 2t}{1 \cdot 3} + \frac{\cos 4t}{3 \cdot 5} + \frac{\cos 6t}{5 \cdot 7} + \dots \right)$
l)	$\begin{cases} 0, & 0 < t < \pi - a \\ 1, & \pi - a < t < \pi + a \\ 0, & \pi + a < t < 2\pi \end{cases}$	$\frac{a}{\pi} - \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\frac{\sin a \cos t}{1} - \frac{\sin 2a \cos 2t}{2} + \frac{\sin 3a \cos 3t}{3} - \dots \right)$

A.2

Fourier transform table

The table is valid for $\Re\{\alpha\} > 0$ and $\Re\{\beta\} > 0$

	$x(t)$	$X(j\Omega)$	$X(f)$
a)	$u\left(t + \frac{T}{2}\right) - u\left(t - \frac{T}{2}\right)$	$T \frac{\sin \Omega T/2}{\Omega T/2}$	$T \frac{\sin \pi f T}{\pi f T} = T \text{sinc}(fT)$
b)	$\frac{\sin Wt}{\pi t} = \frac{W}{\pi} \text{sinc} \frac{Wt}{\pi}$	$u(\Omega + W) - u(\Omega - W)$	$u\left(f + \frac{W}{2\pi}\right) - u\left(f - \frac{W}{2\pi}\right)$
c)	$\begin{cases} 1 - 2\frac{ t }{T}, & t < \frac{T}{2} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$	$\frac{T}{2} \left[\frac{\sin \Omega T/4}{\Omega T/4} \right]^2$	$\frac{T}{2} \text{sinc}^2(Tf/2)$
d)	$e^{-\alpha t} u(t)$	$\frac{1}{j\Omega + \alpha}$	$\frac{1}{j2\pi f + \alpha}$
e)	$e^{-\alpha t }$	$\frac{2\alpha}{\Omega^2 + \alpha^2}$	$\frac{2\alpha}{(2\pi f)^2 + \alpha^2}$
f)	$\frac{1}{\beta - \alpha} [e^{-\alpha t} - e^{-\beta t}] u(t)$	$\frac{1}{(j\Omega + \alpha)(j\Omega + \beta)}$	$\frac{1}{(j2\pi f + \alpha)(j2\pi f + \beta)}$
g)	$te^{-\alpha t} u(t)$	$\frac{1}{(j\Omega + \alpha)^2}$	$\frac{1}{(j2\pi f + \alpha)^2}$
h)	$\frac{t^{n-1}}{(n-1)!} e^{-\alpha t} u(t)$	$\frac{1}{(j\Omega + \alpha)^n}$	$\frac{1}{(j2\pi f + \alpha)^n}$
i)	$e^{-(\alpha t)^2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\alpha} e^{-(\Omega/2\alpha)^2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\alpha} e^{-(\pi f/\alpha)^2}$
j)	$e^{-\alpha t} \sin(\Omega_0 t) u(t)$	$\frac{\Omega_0}{(j\Omega + \alpha)^2 + \Omega_0^2}$	$\frac{\Omega_0}{(j2\pi f + \alpha)^2 + \Omega_0^2}$
	$e^{\alpha t} \sin(\Omega_0 t) u(-t)$	$\frac{-\Omega_0}{(\alpha - j\Omega)^2 + \Omega_0^2}$	$\frac{-\Omega_0}{(\alpha - j2\pi f)^2 + \Omega_0^2}$
k)	$e^{-\alpha t} \cos(\Omega_0 t) u(t)$	$\frac{\alpha + j\Omega}{(j\Omega + \alpha)^2 + \Omega_0^2}$	$\frac{\alpha + j2\pi f}{(j2\pi f + \alpha)^2 + \Omega_0^2}$
	$e^{\alpha t} \cos(\Omega_0 t) u(-t)$	$\frac{\alpha - j\Omega}{(\alpha - j\Omega)^2 + \Omega_0^2}$	$\frac{\alpha - j2\pi f}{(\alpha - j2\pi f)^2 + \Omega_0^2}$
l)	$(\cos \Omega_0 t) \left[u\left(t + \frac{T}{2}\right) - u\left(t - \frac{T}{2}\right) \right]$	$\frac{T}{2} \left[\frac{\sin(\Omega - \Omega_0) \frac{T}{2}}{(\Omega - \Omega_0) \frac{T}{2}} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\sin(\Omega + \Omega_0) \frac{T}{2}}{(\Omega + \Omega_0) \frac{T}{2}} \right]$	$\frac{T}{2} \left[\frac{\sin \pi T(f - f_0)}{\pi T(f - f_0)} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{\sin \pi T(f + f_0)}{\pi T(f + f_0)} \right]$

APPENDIX-B

Resource Manual

B.1 DATASETS

URL: <https://www.deepsig.ai/datasets/>

STRUCTURE OF DATASET:

24 modulations: OOK, ASK4, ASK8, BPSK, QPSK, PSK8, PSK16, PSK32, APSK16, APSK32, APSK64, APSK128, QAM16, QAM32, QAM64, QAM128, QAM256, AM_SSB_WC, AM_SSB_SC, AM_DSB_WC, AM_DSB_SC, FM, GMSK and OQPS. The modulation is onehot encoded so you must check the index of the '1' and select the modulation string from the array above.

26 SNRs per modulation (-20 dB to +30 dB in steps of 2dB).

4096 frames per modulation-SNR combination.

1024 complex time-series samples per frame.

Samples as floating point in-phase and quadrature (I/Q) components, resulting in a (1024,2) frame shape.

2,555,904 frames in total.

Each frame can be retrieved by accessing the HDF5 groups:

X: I/Q components of the frame;

Y: Modulation of the frame (one-hot encoded)

Z: SNR of the frame

Data consist of 24 Modulations --> 26 SNR --> 4096 Frames --> (1024, 2) I/Q Samples. Below is a structural example of the dataset:

B.2 GITHUB REPOSITORY

URL: <https://github.com/Cloudief9/CNN-LSTM>

CODES

CNN-LSTM:

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import h5py
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
import keras
import keras.backend as K
import tensorflow.keras as tk
from keras.layers import LeakyReLU
from time import time
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, ConfusionMatrixDisplay

dataset_file = h5py.File("D:/data/Data
Signals/archive/GOLD_XYZ_OSC.0001_1024.hdf5","r")

base_modulation_classes = ['OOK', '4ASK', '8ASK', 'BPSK', 'QPSK', '8PSK', '16PSK',
'32PSK',
                        '16APSK', '32APSK', '64APSK', '128APSK', '16QAM', '32QAM',
'64QAM',
                        '128QAM', '256QAM', 'AM-SSB-WC', 'AM-SSB-SC', 'AM-DSB-
WC', 'AM-DSB-SC',
                        'FM', 'GMSK', 'OQPSK']

selected_modulation_classes = ['4ASK', 'BPSK', 'QPSK', '16PSK', '16QAM', 'FM',
'AM-DSB-WC', '32APSK']

selected_classes_id = [base_modulation_classes.index(cls) for cls in
selected_modulation_classes]

N_SNR = 4 # from 30 SNR to 22 SNR

X_data = None
```

```

y_data = None

for id in selected_classes_id:
    X_slice = dataset_file['X'][(106496*(id+1) - 4096*N_SNR):106496*(id+1)]
    y_slice = dataset_file['Y'][(106496*(id+1) - 4096*N_SNR):106496*(id+1)]

    if X_data is not None:
        X_data = np.concatenate([X_data, X_slice], axis=0)
        y_data = np.concatenate([y_data, y_slice], axis=0)
    else:
        X_data = X_slice
        y_data = y_slice

X_data = X_data.reshape(len(X_data), 32, 32, 2)

y_data_df = pd.DataFrame(y_data)
for column in y_data_df.columns:
    if sum(y_data_df[column]) == 0:
        y_data_df = y_data_df.drop(columns=[column])

y_data_df.columns = selected_modulation_classes
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X_data, y_data_df, test_size=0.2)

def create_model():
    learning_rate = 0.0001
    i_input = keras.layers.Input(shape=(32,32,1))
    q_input = keras.layers.Input(shape=(32,32,1))

    cnn_q_1 = tk.layers.Conv2D(64, 3, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(q_input)
    cnn_q_1_2 = tk.layers.Conv2D(64, 3, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(cnn_q_1)
    pool_q_1 = tk.layers.MaxPool2D(pool_size=3, strides=2, padding='valid')
(cnn_q_1_2)
    cnn_q_2 = tk.layers.Conv2D(128, 3, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(pool_q_1)
    cnn_q_2_2 = tk.layers.Conv2D(128, 3, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))
(cnn_q_2)
    pool_q_2 = tk.layers.MaxPool2D(pool_size=3, strides=2, padding='valid')
(cnn_q_2_2)

```

```

flatten_q = tk.layers.Flatten()(pool_q_2)

cnn_i_1 = tk.layers.Conv2D(64, 3, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(i_input)
cnn_i_1_2 = tk.layers.Conv2D(64, 3, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(cnn_i_1)
pool_i_1 = tk.layers.MaxPool2D(pool_size=3, strides=2, padding='valid')
(cnn_i_1_2)
cnn_i_2 = tk.layers.Conv2D(128, 3, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(pool_i_1)
cnn_i_2_2 = tk.layers.Conv2D(128, 3, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(cnn_i_2)
pool_i_2 = tk.layers.MaxPool2D(pool_size=3, strides=2, padding='valid')
(cnn_i_2_2)
flatten_i = tk.layers.Flatten()(pool_i_2)

concat = keras.layers.concatenate([flatten_q, flatten_i])

reshape = keras.layers.Reshape((1, -1))(concat)

lstm = tk.layers.LSTM(256, return_sequences=False, dropout=0.5,
recurrent_dropout=0.5)(reshape)

dense1 = keras.layers.Dense(1024, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(lstm)
dropout1 = tk.layers.Dropout(0.5)(dense1)

dense2 = keras.layers.Dense(1024, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(dropout1)
dropout2 = tk.layers.Dropout(0.5)(dense2)

dense3 = keras.layers.Dense(1024, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(dropout2)
dropout3 = tk.layers.Dropout(0.5)(dense3)

dense4 = keras.layers.Dense(256, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(dropout3)
dropout4 = tk.layers.Dropout(0.5)(dense4)

dense5 = keras.layers.Dense(32, activation=LeakyReLU(alpha=0.1))(dropout4)
outputs = keras.layers.Dense(len(selected_classes_id), activation='softmax')(dense5)

model = keras.Model(inputs=[i_input, q_input], outputs=outputs)
model.compile(
    loss='categorical_crossentropy',
    optimizer=tk.optimizers.Adam(learning_rate=learning_rate),
    metrics=['accuracy']
)

```

```

    )
    return model

model = create_model()
batch_size = 64
epochs = 25

path_checkpoint = "model_checkpoint.weights.h5"
es_callback = tk.callbacks.EarlyStopping(monitor="accuracy", min_delta=0,
patience=10)

modelckpt_callback = tk.callbacks.ModelCheckpoint(
    monitor="accuracy",
    filepath=path_checkpoint,
    verbose=1,
    save_weights_only=True,
    save_best_only=True,
)

history = model.fit(
    x=[X_train[:, :, 0], X_train[:, :, 1]],
    y=y_train,
    batch_size=batch_size,
    epochs=epochs,
    validation_data=(X_test[:, :, 0], X_test[:, :, 1]), y_test),
    callbacks=[es_callback, modelckpt_callback],
)

plt.plot(np.c_[history.history['accuracy'], history.history['val_accuracy']])
plt.legend(['accuracy', 'val_accuracy'])
plt.show()

plt.plot(np.c_[history.history['loss'], history.history['val_loss']])
plt.legend(['loss', 'val_loss'])
plt.show()

model_predictions = model.predict([X_test[:, :, 0], X_test[:, :, 1]])

```

```

def convert_to_matrix(logit_list):
    logit_list = list(logit_list)
    return logit_list.index(max(logit_list))

cm = confusion_matrix(
    y_true=list(map(convert_to_matrix, y_test.values)),
    y_pred=list(map(convert_to_matrix, model_predictions)),
)

disp = ConfusionMatrixDisplay(confusion_matrix=cm,
display_labels=selected_modulation_classes)
disp.plot()
plt.show()

model.save_weights('D:/data/Data Signals/CNN_model.weights.h5')

loaded_model = create_model()
loaded_model.load_weights('D:/data/Data Signals/CNN_model.weights.h5')

loss, acc = loaded_model.evaluate([X_test[:, :, :, 0], X_test[:, :, :, 1]], y_test, verbose=2)
print("Restored model, accuracy: {:.2f}%".format(100 * acc))

```

B3. OTHER RESOURCES

https://seh-audio.s3.amazonaws.com/peacock_sounds_1.wav

APPENDIX-C

Experiment Logs

C.1 CNN logs:

Python 3.12.4 | packaged by Anaconda, Inc. | (main, Jun 18 2024, 15:03:56) [MSC
v.1929 64 bit (AMD64)]

Type "copyright", "credits" or "license" for more information.

IPython 8.25.0 -- An enhanced Interactive Python.

```
runfile('D:/data/Python Files/Success2.py', wdir='D:/data/Python Files')
C:\Users\Shivanta Sahoo\anaconda3\Lib\site-packages\keras\src\layers\activations\
leaky_relu.py:41: UserWarning: Argument `alpha` is deprecated. Use `negative_slope`
instead.
```

```
warnings.warn(
```

```
Epoch 1/15
```

```
1639/1639 ----- 0s 266ms/step - accuracy: 0.5845 - loss: 0.8879
```

```
Epoch 1: accuracy improved from -inf to 0.65771, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
```

```
1639/1639 ----- 472s 284ms/step - accuracy: 0.5845 - loss: 0.8878 -
val_accuracy: 0.7754 - val_loss: 0.5018
```

```
Epoch 2/15
```

```
1639/1639 ----- 0s 264ms/step - accuracy: 0.7670 - loss: 0.5075
```

```
Epoch 2: accuracy improved from 0.65771 to 0.77440, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
```

```
1639/1639 ----- 498s 281ms/step - accuracy: 0.7671 - loss: 0.5075 -
val_accuracy: 0.7873 - val_loss: 0.4631
```

```
Epoch 3/15
```

```
1639/1639 ----- 0s 262ms/step - accuracy: 0.7940 - loss: 0.4484
```

```
Epoch 3: accuracy improved from 0.77440 to 0.80283, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
```

```
1639/1639 ----- 458s 280ms/step - accuracy: 0.7940 - loss: 0.4484 -
val_accuracy: 0.8133 - val_loss: 0.4197
```

```
Epoch 4/15
```

```
1639/1639 ----- 0s 263ms/step - accuracy: 0.8248 - loss: 0.3846
```

Epoch 4: accuracy improved from 0.80283 to 0.82697, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 459s 280ms/step - accuracy: 0.8248 - loss: 0.3846 -
val_accuracy: 0.8132 - val_loss: 0.5607
Epoch 5/15
1639/1639 ----- 0s 261ms/step - accuracy: 0.8418 - loss: 0.3498
Epoch 5: accuracy improved from 0.82697 to 0.84550, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 455s 278ms/step - accuracy: 0.8418 - loss: 0.3498 -
val_accuracy: 0.8390 - val_loss: 0.3393
Epoch 6/15
1639/1639 ----- 0s 265ms/step - accuracy: 0.8545 - loss: 0.3185
Epoch 6: accuracy improved from 0.84550 to 0.85965, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 464s 283ms/step - accuracy: 0.8545 - loss: 0.3185 -
val_accuracy: 0.8690 - val_loss: 0.2946
Epoch 7/15
1639/1639 ----- 0s 270ms/step - accuracy: 0.8732 - loss: 0.2785
Epoch 7: accuracy improved from 0.85965 to 0.87645, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 471s 287ms/step - accuracy: 0.8732 - loss: 0.2785 -
val_accuracy: 0.8735 - val_loss: 0.2826
Epoch 8/15
1639/1639 ----- 0s 265ms/step - accuracy: 0.8889 - loss: 0.2466
Epoch 8: accuracy improved from 0.87645 to 0.88957, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 463s 283ms/step - accuracy: 0.8889 - loss: 0.2466 -
val_accuracy: 0.8759 - val_loss: 0.2794
Epoch 9/15
1639/1639 ----- 0s 267ms/step - accuracy: 0.9043 - loss: 0.2148
Epoch 9: accuracy improved from 0.88957 to 0.90380, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 466s 284ms/step - accuracy: 0.9043 - loss: 0.2148 -
val_accuracy: 0.8764 - val_loss: 0.2713
Epoch 10/15
1639/1639 ----- 0s 265ms/step - accuracy: 0.9219 - loss: 0.1802
Epoch 10: accuracy improved from 0.90380 to 0.91793, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5

```
1639/1639 ----- 465s 284ms/step - accuracy: 0.9219 - loss: 0.1802 -  
val_accuracy: 0.8842 - val_loss: 0.2668  
Epoch 11/15  
1639/1639 ----- 0s 264ms/step - accuracy: 0.9339 - loss: 0.1562  
Epoch 11: accuracy improved from 0.91793 to 0.93042, saving model to  
model_checkpoint.weights.h5  
1639/1639 ----- 461s 281ms/step - accuracy: 0.9339 - loss: 0.1562 -  
val_accuracy: 0.8787 - val_loss: 0.2797  
Epoch 12/15  
1639/1639 ----- 0s 264ms/step - accuracy: 0.9463 - loss: 0.1306  
Epoch 12: accuracy improved from 0.93042 to 0.94278, saving model to  
model_checkpoint.weights.h5  
1639/1639 ----- 461s 281ms/step - accuracy: 0.9463 - loss: 0.1307 -  
val_accuracy: 0.8813 - val_loss: 0.2881  
Epoch 13/15  
1639/1639 ----- 0s 266ms/step - accuracy: 0.9594 - loss: 0.1025  
Epoch 13: accuracy improved from 0.94278 to 0.95690, saving model to  
model_checkpoint.weights.h5  
1639/1639 ----- 466s 284ms/step - accuracy: 0.9594 - loss: 0.1025 -  
val_accuracy: 0.8829 - val_loss: 0.3054  
Epoch 14/15  
1639/1639 ----- 0s 268ms/step - accuracy: 0.9706 - loss: 0.0752  
Epoch 14: accuracy improved from 0.95690 to 0.96917, saving model to  
model_checkpoint.weights.h5  
1639/1639 ----- 468s 285ms/step - accuracy: 0.9706 - loss: 0.0752 -  
val_accuracy: 0.8591 - val_loss: 0.4300  
Epoch 15/15  
1639/1639 ----- 0s 273ms/step - accuracy: 0.9771 - loss: 0.0626  
Epoch 15: accuracy improved from 0.96917 to 0.97720, saving model to  
model_checkpoint.weights.h5  
1639/1639 ----- 476s 291ms/step - accuracy: 0.9771 - loss: 0.0626 -  
val_accuracy: 0.8731 - val_loss: 0.4405
```

Important

Figures are displayed in the Plots pane by default. To make them also appear inline in the console, you need to uncheck "Mute inline plotting" under the options menu of Plots.

```
820/820 ----- 33s 39ms/step
C:\Users\Shivanta Sahoo\anaconda3\Lib\site-packages\keras\src\layers\activations\
leaky_relu.py:41: UserWarning: Argument `alpha` is deprecated. Use `negative_slope`
instead.
  warnings.warn(
C:\Users\Shivanta Sahoo\anaconda3\Lib\site-packages\keras\src\saving\
saving_lib.py:576: UserWarning: Skipping variable loading for optimizer 'adam',
because it has 2 variables whereas the saved optimizer has 58 variables.
  saveable.load_own_variables(weights_store.get(inner_path))
820/820 - 31s - 38ms/step - accuracy: 0.8731 - loss: 0.4405
Restored model, accuracy: 87.31%
```

```
2024-07-19 16:37:49.735641: I tensorflow/core/util/port.cc:113] oneDNN custom
operations are on. You may see slightly different numerical results due to floating-point
round-off errors from different computation orders. To turn them off, set the
environment variable `TF_ENABLE_ONEDNN_OPTS=0`.
```

```
2024-07-19 16:37:52.660232: I tensorflow/core/util/port.cc:113] oneDNN custom
operations are on. You may see slightly different numerical results due to floating-point
round-off errors from different computation orders. To turn them off, set the
environment variable `TF_ENABLE_ONEDNN_OPTS=0`.
```

```
2024-07-19 16:38:02.181141: I tensorflow/core/platform/cpu_feature_guard.cc:210]
This TensorFlow binary is optimized to use available CPU instructions in performance-
critical operations.
```

```
To enable the following instructions: AVX2 FMA, in other operations, rebuild
TensorFlow with the appropriate compiler flags.
```

```
2024-07-19 16:38:09.776688: E
tensorflow/core/grappler/optimizers/meta_optimizer.cc:961] remapper failed
```

C2. CNN-LSTM logs

```
runfile('D:/data/Python Files/untitled8.py', wdir='D:/data/Python Files')
C:\Users\Shivanta Sahoo\anaconda3\Lib\site-packages\keras\src\layers\activations\
leaky_relu.py:41: UserWarning: Argument `alpha` is deprecated. Use `negative_slope`
instead.
  warnings.warn(
Epoch 1/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 280ms/step - accuracy: 0.4470 - loss: 1.2316
Epoch 1: accuracy improved from -inf to 0.56349, saving model to
```

model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 496s 298ms/step - accuracy: 0.4470 - loss: 1.2314 -
val_accuracy: 0.7356 - val_loss: 0.5934
Epoch 2/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 273ms/step - accuracy: 0.7273 - loss: 0.5991
Epoch 2: accuracy improved from 0.56349 to 0.74374, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 475s 290ms/step - accuracy: 0.7273 - loss: 0.5990 -
val_accuracy: 0.6993 - val_loss: 0.6448
Epoch 3/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 269ms/step - accuracy: 0.7703 - loss: 0.5148
Epoch 3: accuracy improved from 0.74374 to 0.77397, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 470s 286ms/step - accuracy: 0.7703 - loss: 0.5148 -
val_accuracy: 0.7889 - val_loss: 0.4715
Epoch 4/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 275ms/step - accuracy: 0.7814 - loss: 0.4849
Epoch 4: accuracy improved from 0.77397 to 0.78266, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 480s 293ms/step - accuracy: 0.7814 - loss: 0.4849 -
val_accuracy: 0.7986 - val_loss: 0.4448
Epoch 5/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 273ms/step - accuracy: 0.7882 - loss: 0.4653
Epoch 5: accuracy improved from 0.78266 to 0.78963, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 476s 290ms/step - accuracy: 0.7883 - loss: 0.4652 -
val_accuracy: 0.7851 - val_loss: 0.4629
Epoch 6/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 269ms/step - accuracy: 0.7933 - loss: 0.4501
Epoch 6: accuracy improved from 0.78963 to 0.79838, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 469s 286ms/step - accuracy: 0.7934 - loss: 0.4500 -
val_accuracy: 0.8118 - val_loss: 0.4074
Epoch 7/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 269ms/step - accuracy: 0.8082 - loss: 0.4174
Epoch 7: accuracy improved from 0.79838 to 0.81521, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 469s 286ms/step - accuracy: 0.8082 - loss: 0.4174 -

val_accuracy: 0.8264 - val_loss: 0.3741
Epoch 8/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 268ms/step - accuracy: 0.8279 - loss: 0.3789
Epoch 8: accuracy improved from 0.81521 to 0.83211, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 468s 286ms/step - accuracy: 0.8279 - loss: 0.3789 -
val_accuracy: 0.8397 - val_loss: 0.3525
Epoch 9/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 273ms/step - accuracy: 0.8412 - loss: 0.3531
Epoch 9: accuracy improved from 0.83211 to 0.84111, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 476s 290ms/step - accuracy: 0.8412 - loss: 0.3531 -
val_accuracy: 0.8358 - val_loss: 0.3603
Epoch 10/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 269ms/step - accuracy: 0.8521 - loss: 0.3276
Epoch 10: accuracy improved from 0.84111 to 0.85298, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 470s 287ms/step - accuracy: 0.8521 - loss: 0.3276 -
val_accuracy: 0.8600 - val_loss: 0.3105
Epoch 11/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 272ms/step - accuracy: 0.8592 - loss: 0.3107
Epoch 11: accuracy improved from 0.85298 to 0.86123, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 475s 290ms/step - accuracy: 0.8592 - loss: 0.3107 -
val_accuracy: 0.8652 - val_loss: 0.2969
Epoch 12/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 271ms/step - accuracy: 0.8686 - loss: 0.2891
Epoch 12: accuracy improved from 0.86123 to 0.87034, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 473s 289ms/step - accuracy: 0.8686 - loss: 0.2891 -
val_accuracy: 0.8529 - val_loss: 0.3119
Epoch 13/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 272ms/step - accuracy: 0.8758 - loss: 0.2757
Epoch 13: accuracy improved from 0.87034 to 0.87598, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 475s 290ms/step - accuracy: 0.8758 - loss: 0.2757 -
val_accuracy: 0.8798 - val_loss: 0.2633
Epoch 14/25

1639/1639 ----- 0s 269ms/step - accuracy: 0.8792 - loss: 0.2632
Epoch 14: accuracy improved from 0.87598 to 0.88223, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 469s 286ms/step - accuracy: 0.8792 - loss: 0.2632 -
val_accuracy: 0.8814 - val_loss: 0.2577
Epoch 15/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 269ms/step - accuracy: 0.8873 - loss: 0.2492
Epoch 15: accuracy improved from 0.88223 to 0.88864, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 469s 286ms/step - accuracy: 0.8873 - loss: 0.2492 -
val_accuracy: 0.8858 - val_loss: 0.2480
Epoch 16/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 268ms/step - accuracy: 0.8922 - loss: 0.2391
Epoch 16: accuracy improved from 0.88864 to 0.89307, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 468s 286ms/step - accuracy: 0.8922 - loss: 0.2391 -
val_accuracy: 0.8888 - val_loss: 0.2440
Epoch 17/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 267ms/step - accuracy: 0.8965 - loss: 0.2267
Epoch 17: accuracy improved from 0.89307 to 0.89893, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 466s 285ms/step - accuracy: 0.8965 - loss: 0.2267 -
val_accuracy: 0.8890 - val_loss: 0.2373
Epoch 18/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 271ms/step - accuracy: 0.9055 - loss: 0.2097
Epoch 18: accuracy improved from 0.89893 to 0.90416, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 473s 289ms/step - accuracy: 0.9055 - loss: 0.2097 -
val_accuracy: 0.8853 - val_loss: 0.2468
Epoch 19/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 278ms/step - accuracy: 0.9101 - loss: 0.2024
Epoch 19: accuracy improved from 0.90416 to 0.90794, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 484s 295ms/step - accuracy: 0.9101 - loss: 0.2024 -
val_accuracy: 0.8982 - val_loss: 0.2235
Epoch 20/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 277ms/step - accuracy: 0.9145 - loss: 0.1902
Epoch 20: accuracy improved from 0.90794 to 0.91357, saving model to

```
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 482s 294ms/step - accuracy: 0.9145 - loss: 0.1902 -
val_accuracy: 0.8920 - val_loss: 0.2436
Epoch 21/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 280ms/step - accuracy: 0.9189 - loss: 0.1803
Epoch 21: accuracy improved from 0.91357 to 0.91852, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 487s 297ms/step - accuracy: 0.9189 - loss: 0.1803 -
val_accuracy: 0.9010 - val_loss: 0.2169
Epoch 22/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 273ms/step - accuracy: 0.9233 - loss: 0.1690
Epoch 22: accuracy improved from 0.91852 to 0.92272, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 477s 291ms/step - accuracy: 0.9233 - loss: 0.1690 -
val_accuracy: 0.8981 - val_loss: 0.2277
Epoch 23/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 275ms/step - accuracy: 0.9298 - loss: 0.1597
Epoch 23: accuracy improved from 0.92272 to 0.92840, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 480s 293ms/step - accuracy: 0.9298 - loss: 0.1597 -
val_accuracy: 0.9033 - val_loss: 0.2170
Epoch 24/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 275ms/step - accuracy: 0.9320 - loss: 0.1535
Epoch 24: accuracy improved from 0.92840 to 0.93253, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 479s 293ms/step - accuracy: 0.9320 - loss: 0.1535 -
val_accuracy: 0.9014 - val_loss: 0.2233
Epoch 25/25
1639/1639 ----- 0s 275ms/step - accuracy: 0.9382 - loss: 0.1417
Epoch 25: accuracy improved from 0.93253 to 0.93731, saving model to
model_checkpoint.weights.h5
1639/1639 ----- 479s 293ms/step - accuracy: 0.9382 - loss: 0.1418 -
val_accuracy: 0.9139 - val_loss: 0.2028
820/820 ----- 33s 40ms/step
C:\Users\Shivanta Sahoo\anaconda3\Lib\site-packages\keras\src\layers\activations\
leaky_relu.py:41: UserWarning: Argument `alpha` is deprecated. Use `negative_slope`
instead.
warnings.warn(
```

```
C:\Users\Shivanta Sahoo\anaconda3\Lib\site-packages\keras\src\saving\
saving_lib.py:576: UserWarning: Skipping variable loading for optimizer 'adam',
because it has 2 variables whereas the saved optimizer has 64 variables.
  saveable.load_own_variables(weights_store.get(inner_path))
820/820 - 32s - 39ms/step - accuracy: 0.9139 - loss: 0.2028
Restored model, accuracy: 91.39%
```

```
2024-07-19 23:12:35.117183: E
tensorflow/core/grappler/optimizers/meta_optimizer.cc:961] remapper failed:
```

APPENDIX-D

Samples from dataset

D.1

D.2

D.3

D.4

xlvi

xlvi